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3D INVERSION OF CHROMOSPHERIC STRUCTURES

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De corazon
Andreu

Resumen

Esta tesis aborda el desafío de inferir el vector del campo magnético en el plasma cromosférico, un problema persistente en la astrofísica solar. Esta investigación tiene como objetivo desarrollar nuevas herramientas numéricas para mejorar la eficiencia y precisión de la inferencia del campo magnético en la atmósfera solar. La información sobre el campo magnético solar está codificada en la polarización de la radiación electromagnética que emerge del Sol. Esta polarización es sensible al campo magnético a través de los efectos Zeeman y Hanle. Nuestras herramientas más poderosas para el diagnóstico del campo magnético son las técnicas de inversión. Generalmente, estas técnicas constan de dos partes: un sintetizador capaz de resolver el problema de transferencia radiativa (RT) y un optimizador que encuentra los parámetros físicos (como la temperatura, velocidad y el campo magnético, entre otros) que, al ser introducidos en el sintetizador, ajustan un conjunto de datos determinado.

El primer problema de investigación que hemos abordado en esta tesis es la aceleración de las técnicas de inversión basadas en el efecto Zeeman en líneas cromosféricas. Excepto en las capas más profundas de la fotosfera solar, las líneas espectrales en el Sol se forman fuera del equilibrio termodinámico local (NLTE). El problema de RT en condiciones NLTE es no lineal y no local, y su solución es computacionalmente costosa, especialmente en comparación con el problema lineal y local en LTE. El problema de RT, y por lo tanto el sintetizador, es el claro cuello de botella de estas técnicas de inversión. Hemos aprovechado el potencial de las técnicas de aprendizaje automático, específicamente las redes neuronales de grafos (GNNs), para omitir por completo la solución del problema de RT. Al entrenar y aplicar la red a la línea Ca II en 8542 Å hemos demostrado que una GNN no solo puede proporcionar un conjunto lo suficientemente preciso de poblaciones en NLTE, reduciendo así el problema de RT a una única y rápida solución directa de la ecuación de RT, sino que el código de inversión resultante es aproximadamente 1000 veces

más rápido en comparación con el método tradicional que resuelve el problema detallado de RT.

Nuestro segundo objetivo ha sido evaluar el impacto de algunas de las aproximaciones que suelen considerarse en el estudio de los filamentos solares y prominencias. La mayoría de los estudios sobre el campo magnético de estas estructuras se basa en el análisis de los perfiles espectropolarimétricos de los tripletes de He I en 10830 Å y D3 en 5876 Å, que muestran señales de polarización por dispersión y características tanto de los efectos Hanle como Zeeman. Debido a las particularidades de su formación, a menudo se interpretan mediante un modelo de bloque de propiedades constantes que ignora los efectos de RT. Sin embargo, no es raro inferir espesores ópticos cercanos a la unidad o superiores para el bloque en el triplete de He I 10830 Å. Hemos estudiado el impacto de los efectos de RT y de la iluminación diferencial entre los componentes del triplete en el triplete de He I 10830 Å en un modelo de bloque de propiedades constantes. Hemos demostrado que, para profundidades ópticas del orden de la unidad y superiores a lo largo de la normal del bloque, los efectos de RT tienen un impacto significativo en la polarización por dispersión emergente. También hemos evaluado cómo los efectos de RT pueden impactar la fiabilidad del campo magnético inferido, lo que potencialmente puede resultar en la interpretación errónea de su magnitud en un orden de magnitud en los peores escenarios.

Finalmente, hemos abordado el problema de la inversión de datos espectropolarimétricos en prominencias, considerando los efectos de RT en completo 3D. Para ello, hemos desarrollado un módulo atómico para la solución de las ecuaciones de equilibrio estadístico y el cálculo de los coeficientes de RT para el triplete de He I 10830 Å, teniendo en cuenta la interferencia cuántica y la iluminación diferencial. Este módulo es parte del código POLARIS, un código de inversión en 3D que hemos desarrollado durante esta tesis y que es capaz de invertir datos espectropolarimétricos en completo 3D resolviendo un problema de minimización sin restricciones con un enfoque sin discretización en malla. Debido a limitaciones de tiempo, solo hemos podido incluir resultados preliminares de su aplicación a los datos espectropolarimétricos en esta tesis. No obstante, estos resultados parecen muy prometedores, y esta investigación continuará y se completará en un futuro cercano.

Abstract

This thesis addresses the challenge of inferring the magnetic field vector in chromospheric plasma, a longstanding issue in solar astrophysics. This research aims at developing new numerical tools to improve the efficiency and accuracy of the magnetic field inference in the solar atmosphere. The information on the solar magnetic field is encoded in the polarization of the electromagnetic radiation emerging from the Sun. This polarization is sensitive to the magnetic field via the Zeeman and Hanle effects. Our most powerful tools for magnetic field diagnosis are inversion techniques. Generally, these techniques consist of two parts, a forward solver capable of solving the radiation transfer (RT) problem, and an optimizer to find the physical parameters (such as temperature, velocity, and the magnetic field, among others) that, when fed into the forward solver, fit a given set of data.

The first research problem we have tackled in this thesis is the acceleration of inversion techniques based on the Zeeman effect in chromospheric lines. Except in the deepest layers of the solar photosphere, spectral lines in the Sun form outside of Local Thermodynamic Equilibrium (NLTE). The RT problem under NLTE conditions is both non-linear and non-local and its solution is computationally expensive, especially when compared with the linear and local LTE problem. The RT problem, and thus the forward solver, is the clear bottleneck of these inversion techniques. We have leveraged the potential of machine learning techniques, specifically Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), to completely bypass the solution of the RT problem. By training and applying the network to the Ca II line at 8542 Å we have demonstrated that a GNN can not only provide an accurate enough set of populations in NLTE, thus reducing the RT problem to a single and fast forward solution of the RT equation, but the resulting inversion code is about 1000 faster when compared to the traditional method which solves the detailed RT problem.

Our second objective has been assessing the impact of some of the approx-

imations usually considered in the study of solar filaments and prominences. Most of the studies on the magnetic field of these structures is based on the analysis of the spectro-polarimetric profiles of He I triplets at 10830 Å and D3 at 5876 Å, which show scattering polarization signals and features of both Hanle and Zeeman effects. Due to the particularities of their formation, they are often interpreted by means of a constant property slab model neglecting RT effects. However, it is not rare to infer optical thickness of unity and larger for the slab in the He I 10830 Å triplet. We have studied the impact of RT effects and of the differential illumination between the triplet components in the He I 10830 Å triplet in a constant property slab model. We have demonstrated that, for optical depths of order unity and above along the normal of the slab, RT effects have a significant impact on the emerging scattering polarization. We have also assessed how RT effects can impact the reliability of the inferred magnetic field, which can potentially result in the misinterpretation of its strength in an order of magnitude in the worst case scenarios.

Finally, we have tackled the problem of the inversion of spectro-polarimetric data in prominences considering RT effects in full 3D. To this end we have developed an atomic module for the solution of the statistical equilibrium equations and the calculation of the RT coefficients for the He I 10830 Å triplet, accounting for quantum interference and differential illumination. This module is part of the POLARIS code, a 3D inversion code that we have developed during this thesis and that is capable of inverting spectro-polarimetric data in full 3D by solving an unconstrained minimization problem with a meshfree approach. Due to time constraints, we have only been able to include preliminary results of its application to spectro-polarimetric data in this thesis. Nevertheless, these results seem really promising, and this research will be continued and completed in the near future.

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1

Introduction

*Nature is a labyrinth in which the very haste you move with
will make you lose your way.*

Francis Bacon

1.1 The Solar Atmosphere

The Sun, the central star of the solar system, has a capital role in both our life and the understanding we have of the Universe. It is our closest cosmic source of energy, providing the necessary conditions to sustain life on Earth. At its core the Sun resembles a giant nuclear fusion reactor, where hydrogen nuclei are converted into helium nuclei, releasing energy in the process. The vast amounts of energy that the Sun emits in the form of heat and light not only illuminates Earth, but also provides a unique opportunity to study the structure and physical processes of stars in detail. The Sun is the only star resolved in detail in the sky, its proximity allows us to closely study very important physical processes like plasma physics, magnetic fields, space weather, radiation transfer, atomic physics, and many others, making it a unique astrophysical laboratory.

Outside of the radiative core of the Sun, a wide variety of phenomena takes place. Going radially outwards, we first find the convection zone, where convective motions transport the heat generated in the core to the surface, also dragging the frozen magnetic fields along. We then find the solar surface, the layer that we can see with the naked eye. Here the plasma is rarefied enough for the radiation to start escaping from the Sun.

Outward from the surface, we find the solar atmosphere. Although the

energy that powers the Sun is generated in its core, the radiation we receive from the Sun is emitted from the solar atmosphere, where energy is transported by photons that can eventually escape and reach Earth. The atmosphere itself is a complex and dynamic layer hosting interesting events and structures like e.g. sunspots, flares, coronal mass ejections, and prominences and filaments. All of them related to magnetic fields and its complex interaction with the solar plasma. The information about their physical properties and their interaction is encoded in the emitted radiation, i.e., the solar spectrum.

The deepest layer of the atmosphere is the photosphere. Due to the overshooting of the convective motions, most of the photosphere is covered with the granular convection pattern. When the magnetic field emerges, dragged up from the tachocline (the interface between the radiative and convective layers, where the magnetic fields are formed) by buoyancy forces, and the magnetic flux is strong enough, the convection is inhibited, forming the so-called sunspots, so-named because they look darker than the surrounding photosphere. Around sunspots, strong magnetic fields (though with much less magnetic flux) form the faculae. Outside these so-called active regions, the quiet areas of the photosphere are also permeated by magnetic fields, though their strength is up to two orders of magnitude weaker than in sunspots, and the field lines are much more intricate and tangled at scales below the resolving power of current telescopes (100 km Bellot Rubio and Orozco Suárez [2019], Borrero and Ichimoto [2011]).

Continuing outward we find the chromosphere, a plasma shell above the photosphere extending a few thousand kilometers. In the chromosphere, the density of the plasma decreases rapidly outward, the magnetic field starts dominating the plasma dynamics, and the temperature starts increasing up to 10 000 K (see the review by Carlsson et al. [2019]).

Besides other clear photospheric activity counterparts, the whole chromospheric volume is pervaded by high velocity jets or spicules that protrude into the corona. Solar spicules play an important role on the mass balance of the solar atmosphere, since they carry about a hundred times the mass of the solar wind. The chromospheric material is also found as magnetically levitating clouds embedded in the hot corona, the so-called prominences. The magnetic field is key to form all these structures, though the actual geometry and strength of the field is still barely constrained by observations.

The outermost layer of the atmosphere is the corona, just above the transition region, a very thin layer where the plasma temperature increases from tens of thousands to a million kelvin in a few hundred kilometers (Judge and Centeno [2008]). The corona is extremely rarefied and the magnetic field draws nice large scale loops, dominating the physics of this layer. What physical pro-

cesses are responsible for the heating of the chromosphere and the corona are still a matter of debate (Aschwanden et al. [2001]), but it is believed that the magnetic field play a crucial role.

The solar magnetic field is the main driver of the solar activity and a wide range of phenomena, such as sunspots, flares, coronal mass ejections, prominences and filaments (Borrero and Ichimoto [2011], Cliver et al. [2022], Díaz Baso et al. [2019a]), or events on Earth like auroras, geomagnetic storms, and the space weather (Temmer [2021]). Consequently, it is crucial to understand how the magnetic field is generated, how it interacts with the plasma, and how the different layers of the solar atmosphere are magnetically connected. To achieve this understanding as well as the prediction capability necessary for space weather forecasting we need to be able to infer the magnetic field vector (its strength and direction) from the available observables.

The information on the magnetic field is encoded in the polarization of spectral lines in the solar spectrum. The most relevant mechanisms producing polarization in spectral lines in the solar atmosphere are the Zeeman effect, anisotropic radiation pumping, and the Hanle effect. The Zeeman effect is the splitting of the degenerate magnetic sublevels of a given atomic level due to the presence of a magnetic field. This in turn results in the splitting of the magnetic components of the ensuing spectral line that produce, in general, both linear and circular polarization (Zeeman [1897]). In particular, the linear (circular) polarization is determined by the component of the magnetic field perpendicular (parallel) to the line of sight. Anisotropic radiation pumping is produced by the absorption and scattering of anisotropic radiation. This leads to population imbalances and quantum interference between the degenerate sublevels of an atomic level (see Trujillo Bueno [2001], Landi Degl'Innocenti and Landolfi [2004]). The resulting selective absorption and emission processes generate the so-called scattering linear polarization. The Hanle effect is the modification of the scattering polarization in the presence of a magnetic field (see Hanle [1924], Stenflo [1994], Trujillo Bueno [2001], Landi Degl'Innocenti and Landolfi [2004]). The Hanle effect is sensitive to magnetic field strengths whose Zeeman splitting is comparable to the inverse lifetime of the line level under consideration. While dependent on the spectral line, the magnetic field sensitivity of the Hanle effect is typically between 10^{-3} and 100 G.

The magnetic field inference in filaments and prominences is of particular interest in regard to space weather and its impact on the Earth's magnetosphere, as they can build up magnetic energy which can be eventually released in the form of flares and coronal mass ejections.

1.2 Filaments and prominences

Solar filaments and prominences stand out as a fundamental magnetic structure of the solar corona. Although they are variable structures and can appear in different shapes (difficulting statistical studies, see the review by Mackay et al. [2010]), they can be defined as relatively cool and dense plasma structures embedded and suspended in the hot corona, thermally isolated from it. When observed on the solar disk, they appear as dark filamentary structures (hence the name filament), while when observed on the limb, they appear as bright translucent structures against the dark background of space (hence the name prominence). They are the same structure, but observed from different perspectives. Consequently, in this work, we use the terms filament and prominence interchangeably except when referring to a particular observation.

Filaments are often classified into two types depending on the region of the Sun where they are found. Quiescent filaments are found in the quiet Sun, and they are long-lived structures that can last for weeks (see e.g., Zirker et al. [1998]). Active filaments are found in active regions and are shorter-lived structures that can last for hours or days, often associated with flares and coronal mass ejections (Moore and LaBonte [1980]).

Filaments can be understood as a magnetic field skeleton running through a central spine going along its length and filled with cool plasma, feet extending from both ends of the spine and connecting to the underlying photosphere, and barbs extending from the spine outwards and often connecting to the chromosphere below (see Lin et al. [2008]). Filaments are made up of thread-like structures, which become observable when they are filled with cool plasma. This explains why the filaments can sometimes fade away and then reappear, as not all their threads are filled simultaneously.

Filaments are one of the most evident manifestations of magnetic fields in the solar atmosphere, since they are the only reason of their existence, supporting them against gravity and isolating them from the surrounding corona. They signal regions of the solar atmosphere (specially at coronal heights) where the magnetic field has a particular and unusual configuration, and therefore are key for the understanding of the solar atmosphere.

For decades, filaments have been known to form above polarity inversion lines (PILs, Babcock and Babcock [1955]), i.e., a boundary between regions with opposite magnetic field polarity on the photosphere. Although it has been known for a long time that these structures are suspended in the corona by magnetic fields, the exact nature of these fields and their configuration is still a matter of debate, with many models and observations differing on both their configuration and strength.

1.3 Filament magnetic field models

Several magnetic field models are considered in the literature, which try to explain the magnetic structure of filaments while neglecting its dynamic nature, the fact that they are observed in neutral lines in a very low collision plasma, and postponing the discussion on their formation.

Since the the ratio of the thermal pressure to the magnetic pressure (know as plasma β) is small, the magnetic field is the dominant force and the plasma moves along the magnetic field lines. Nevertheless, the weight of the plasma needs to be accounted for, as it contributes (or even determines in some models) the shape of the magnetic field in the filament model.

Nowadays, there are two main magnetic models of filaments, the sheared arcade and the flux rope (see Gibson [2018] and reference therein for a detailed description).

In the sheared arcade model, the filament forms from a collection of patches of opposite polarity in each side of the PIL that have been deformed or "sheared" along the magnetic neutral line. This shearing creates dipped magnetic fields, regions where the magnetic field lines curve downward, providing a stable environment for the dense filament plasma. The magnetic field in these dips can counteract the gravitational force, supporting the plasma through magnetic tension forces. The sheared arcade model is particularly compelling in three-dimensional scenarios, where shearing motions can compress the magnetic field, leading to the formation of these dips within the arcade structure. This model suggests that filaments may form in pre-existing magnetic dips created by the natural distribution of magnetic flux on the Sun's surface.

By contrast, the flux rope model describes a structure where magnetic field lines twist around a central axis, creating a helical or rope-like configuration. This model involves a topologically distinct magnetic system, where the filament is supported by a magnetic field that wraps around itself, creating dips that can stabilize the plasma. Flux ropes can form through various processes, such as the twisting of magnetic fields at the solar surface, the reconnection of sheared magnetic field lines, or the emergence of pre-existing twisted fields. Unlike the sheared arcade, flux ropes are characterized by their internal twist and are more prone to instabilities, such as the kink instability, which can lead to eruptions. Although locally similar, both models differ significantly in their magnetic topology, the processes that lead to their formation, and their stability.

Both of these models need to be put in the context of the solar atmosphere, where background magnetic fields, plasma flows, and other physical processes can influence the shape, stability, and evolution of the filament magnetic field

configuration. Given the fact that the observations of filaments are usually made in neutral atomic lines (i.e., H alpha, He I 10830Å which is a triplet system of neutral helium, among others), it is also important to understand what mechanism of ion-neutral coupling is needed to suspend the filament.

1.4 Filament formation and dynamics

The formation mechanism of filaments is still a matter of debate, since there is no model that can explain the wide range of complex characteristics observed. There are three main mechanisms that are considered to be plausible for filling the filament with cool plasma (since there is not enough density in the corona, the plasma must come from the chromosphere or the photosphere). The first is the evaporation-condensation model (Engvold and Jensen [1977]), where the plasma is evaporated from the chromosphere due to heating and condensates near the top of the loop. The second is the direct injection model (Wang [1999], Chae [2001]), where the plasma is injected directly from the chromosphere to the corona. The driver of the injection force is believed to be the local reconnection of parasitic polarities either at the PIL or away from it. The third is the levitation model (Rust and Kumar [1994]), where plasma is lifted from the chromosphere by the rise of magnetic fields at the PIL due to either reconnection or flux emergence.

Filaments are dynamic structures that can also oscillate, erupt, and change their shape in a matter of hours or days. More observations with higher cadence and resolution are needed to fully understand the dynamics of filaments.

1.5 Filament observational landscape

The filament models must be supported by observational constrains. The most direct way we have to acquire information about the magnetic topology is through spectro-polarimetric inversions of spectral line polarization (del Toro Iniesta and Ruiz Cobo [2016]). Among all the lines in the solar spectrum, only a few are suitable for this task, since they need to be observable in filaments and have sensitivity to the magnetic field. The most used lines in the study of filaments are the He I triplets at 10830 Å and D3 at 5876 Å (Landi Degl’Innocenti [1982], Avrett et al. [1994]), and the H I Balmer alpha line ($H\alpha$). While $H\alpha$ is a strong line even in filaments, it is generally optically thick and its modelling is complex (Štěpán et al. [2019]).

Since the 1970’s, studies have been conducted to determine the magnetic field in filaments. The earlier works (see the review by Paletou and Aulanier [2003]) posed a mostly horizontal magnetic field (i.e., parallel to the solar sur-

face) with a strength of 3–15 G in quiescent prominences. This was similarly posed with later observations by Casini et al. [2003], who found field strengths of about 10–20 G and mostly horizontal fields deviating 20–30 degrees from the prominence axis. Levens et al. [2016] found a mostly horizontal field in a tornado and a bubble prominence, with field strengths of about 20–40 G, but with a more vertical fields in the case of an eruptive prominence.

By contrast, Merenda et al. [2006], studying a polar crown prominence above the limb, showed evidence of almost vertical fields (25 degrees from the vertical) of about 30 G. This was later supported by observations from Martínez González et al. [2015], showing mostly vertical helical fields of about 10–20 G at a quiescent prominence above the limb.

At the light of these observations, the magnetic field configuration of filaments is still a matter of debate for several reasons. First, the complexity in the acquisition and the signal to noise of the spectro-polarimetric observations needed to determine with enough precision the magnetic field configuration. Second, the intrinsic ambiguity in the determination of the magnetic field from the Hanle effect, making the inverse problem of the magnetic field in filaments from the He I lines to have multiple (2 to 4) solutions. Moreover, due to the complexity of the physical processes involved in the generation and transfer of polarized radiation, strong simplifications are often considered in the modeling, like the assumption of a constant properties slab or neglecting 3D radiative transfer effects, complicating the accurate and unambiguous determination of the magnetic field.

Despite decades of studies, we still lack a clear picture of the magnetic field configuration in filaments. To help solving this problem, new and powerful telescopes have been recently built or are under development, like the Daniel K. Inouye Solar Telescope in Manua Kea (DKIST Rimmele et al. [2020]) and the European Solar Telescope in La Palma (EST Quintero Noda et al. [2022]). These telescopes will provide observations with better spatial, temporal, and spectral resolution and better signal-to-noise ratio and polarimetric sensitivity. However, with the improvement in the quality of the observations, the tools for their interpretation must also improve, as the current inversion tools neglect radiative transfer and 3D effects. Such effects are known to be important in the formation of the spectro-polarimetric signals of the lines used in the magnetic field inference (Štěpán and Trujillo Bueno [2013], Jaume Bestard et al. [2021b], Trujillo Bueno and Asensio Ramos [2007]). It thus becomes apparent that new approaches and tools are needed to fully extract the information contained in the observations. In addition, these tools need to be fast to keep up with the

large amounts of data to be produced by the new generation of telescopes.

1.6 Thesis outline

This thesis aims to push forward our knowledge of filaments by providing new tools (both theoretical and computational) to infer their magnetic field in full 3D. This work is divided in four main chapters, each one focusing on a different aspect of the problem. First we introduce the necessary theoretical basis for the modeling of polarization in spectral lines (Chap. 2). Then we focus on the acceleration of existing inversion tools, as improving the efficiency of inference methods is a critical challenge in view of the increasingly large volume of available data (Chap. 3). We then present a new theoretical approach to model the He I 10830 Å triplet, relaxing the flat-spectrum approximation (Chap 4). Finally, we propose a new method to determine the magnetic field in filaments, developing a 3D inversion code for the He I 10830 Å triplet accounting for radiative transfer in full 3D (Chap. 5), and applying it to observations of a prominence (Chap. 6). This new tool will allow us to improve our understanding of the magnetic field through the accurate inference of the physical quantities involved, leveraging the latest advances in inference tools and observational data. By attempting the reconstruction of the magnetic field structure as a whole, this research aims to answer critical questions about the magnetic field topology in filaments. Finally, chapter 7 concludes with a discussion of the implications of our findings, suggesting directions for future research.

2

Theoretical background

It does not make any difference how beautiful your guess is.

*It does not make any difference how smart you are,
who made the guess, or what his name is.*

If it disagrees with the experiment it is wrong.

Richard P. Feynman (chapter 7, “Seeking New Laws,” p. 156)

In astrophysics, except for a few exceptions in the solar system, the physical properties of astronomical objects cannot be directly measured. Instead, we most often infer their physical properties from the measure of the much more accessible electromagnetic radiation they emit. This radiation is the result of the emission, absorption, and scattering of photons by the atoms and molecules in those objects. Therefore, comprehending the radiation field (and its polarization properties), the composition of matter (the atomic species within the plasma and their excitation state), and the processes involved in the matter-radiation interaction is essential for the modeling of the physical properties of astronomical objects.

In the first part of this chapter we describe the radiation field and its polarization in terms of the polarization tensor (section 2.1). We then explore how the state of the atoms in the plasma is described in quantum theory (section 2.2). Then, we describe the radiation-matter interaction, showing the relevant equations and how they are solved with the goal of modelling the emergent spectrum (section 2.3). Finally, we explore the inverse problem, i.e., the process of inferring the physical properties of the emitting plasma from the observed spectrum (section 2.4).

2.1 Radiation field

The radiation field is described in classical physics as an electromagnetic wave. If we assume a monochromatic plane wave¹, propagating parallel to the z axis of a right-handed reference frame, the electric and magnetic fields are related by the equation: $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{r}, t) \propto \mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, t)$, where \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} are the electric and magnetic field vectors, respectively, \mathbf{n} is the direction of propagation, and \mathbf{r} is the position vector. From this equation, derived from the Maxwell equations, it is clear that $\mathbf{E} \perp \mathbf{B} \perp \mathbf{n}$ and $|\mathbf{E}| \propto |\mathbf{B}|$ where, in this case, we have defined $\mathbf{n} \parallel \hat{z}$.

An electromagnetic wave can be characterized by its frequency ν (or equivalently, wavelength λ), intensity I , wave vector $\mathbf{k} \parallel \mathbf{n}$, and polarization state (temporal evolution of the electric and magnetic field vectors in the plane perpendicular to the propagation direction). In the next section we focus on the polarization state, on how it can be described and how it characterizes the radiation field.

2.1.1 Polarization of light and the Stokes parameters

The polarization is a very important property of the radiation field since it carries information about the scattering geometry and the magnetic field of the emitting object. In this thesis we describe the polarization with the formalism of the Stokes parameters. The Stokes parameters are four quantities (I , Q , U , V) that describe the intensity of the radiation (I), the linear oscillation of the electric² field vector (Q and U), and its circular oscillation (V). In general, the polarization state is a combination of both linear and circular oscillations, i.e., an ellipse in the plane perpendicular to the direction of propagation.

We can derive the Stokes parameters from the oscillation of the electric field. The electric field corresponding to a monochromatic plane wave propagating along the z axis of a right-handed reference frame is given by

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \mathbf{E}_x \cos(kz - \omega t + \phi) + \mathbf{E}_y \cos(kz - \omega t), \quad (2.1)$$

where \mathbf{E}_x and \mathbf{E}_y are the components of the amplitude along the x and y axes, \mathbf{k} is the wave vector (parallel to the direction of propagation \hat{z}), \mathbf{r} is the position, ω is the frequency, t is the time, and ϕ is the phase. The choice of the reference

¹Which is a fantastic approximation given the huge distances from the source and the relatively short wavelengths of the visible light, i.e., 1 AU and 400-1000 nm approximately.

²Since electric and magnetic fields are related by the equation $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{r}, t) \propto \mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, t)$, equivalent derivation exists for the magnetic field. We will focus on the electric field for historical reasons and convenience.

frame for the electric field is arbitrary (the \hat{x} and \hat{y} directions), and determines the reference direction for the linear polarization. The Stokes parameters are then defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 I &= \varepsilon_x^* \varepsilon_x + \varepsilon_y^* \varepsilon_y = |\varepsilon_x|^2 + |\varepsilon_y|^2 \quad , \\
 Q &= \varepsilon_x^* \varepsilon_x - \varepsilon_y^* \varepsilon_y = |\varepsilon_x|^2 - |\varepsilon_y|^2 \quad , \\
 U &= \varepsilon_x^* \varepsilon_y + \varepsilon_y^* \varepsilon_x = 2 \operatorname{Re}(\varepsilon_x \varepsilon_y^*) \quad , \\
 V &= i(\varepsilon_x^* \varepsilon_y - \varepsilon_y^* \varepsilon_x) = 2 \operatorname{Im}(\varepsilon_x \varepsilon_y^*) ,
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2.2}$$

where $\varepsilon_j = E_j e^{i\phi_j}$ ($j = x, y$, $\phi_x = \phi$, $\phi_y = 0$). We can see that I is independent of the reference frame, while Q , U , and V are not. V , in particular, is dependent on the *right-handedness* of the reference frame, but not directly on the orientation of the x and y axes. The visual representation of the polarization state can be seen in Fig. 2.1, showing the empirical definition of the Stokes parameters.

FIGURE 2.1— Visual representation of the Stokes parameters Q , U , and V in terms of the oscillation of the electric field for a given reference frame (Landi Degl’Innocenti and Landolfi [2004]).

One important aspect to highlight about the electromagnetic radiation (and

therefore the Stokes parameters) is that, the electric field cannot be instantly measured. What we observe is the cumulative signal over a period of time Δt , so the I , Q , U , and V are actually the time-averaged values of the quantities in Eq. (2.2) related to the electric field. This is because of the intrinsic meaning of polarization (change with time of the oscillation direction of \mathbf{E}) and due to instrumental reasons. The integration time Δt will depend on the characteristics of the radiation field and the detector used to measure it.

In practice, as we cannot directly measure electric fields nor the polarization with detectors in the optical and near-infrared range, we measure the intensity of the radiation that comes out of a carefully designed system of polarizing filters and retarders (modulation optics), that allows us to determine the underlying polarization state through a process called demodulation. This way of sensing the unknown polarization state as a combination of intensity measurements when the radiation passes through a known modulating optics system introduces some uncertainties in the measurement that are important in their interpretation (see section 2.4).

2.1.2 Polarization tensor formalism

The polarization, as described in section 2.1.1, can be expressed in a more convenient way by using a formalism that is invariant under the rotation of the reference frame. This representation is also useful to describe the interaction with the plasma.

The first step to arrive at such description, is to find how the polarization transforms under a rotation of the reference frame. One useful intermediate step is to define a complex 2x2 matrix \mathbf{I} , called the polarization tensor, from the complex quantities ε_j of Eq. (2.2) as

$$I_{ij} = k \varepsilon_i \varepsilon_j^* \quad (i = x, y), \quad (2.3)$$

where k is a constant. The tensor \mathbf{I} is Hermitian and positive semidefinite by definition, since it must satisfy $I_{ij} = I_{ji}^*$, and its trace, which is the total intensity, must be real and positive.

We note that we can easily express the Stokes parameters in terms of the polarization tensor. To express the polarization tensor in a different reference frame, we can apply a rotation matrix as

$$\mathcal{I}' = \mathbf{R} \mathcal{I} \mathbf{R}^*,$$

where, if the basis vectors are orthonormal, then the rotation matrix fulfills $\mathbf{R}^{-1} = \mathbf{R}^*$. This tensor is a rank 3 Cartesian tensor, and it can be expressed

in terms of spherical tensors. A spherical tensor of rank k transforms linearly under rotation as

$$\mathcal{T}'_{qq'} = \sum_{pp'} D_{pq}^k(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) D_{p'q'}^k(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)^* \mathcal{T}_{pp'}, \quad (2.4)$$

where α, β, γ are the Euler angles of the rotation that brings the old reference frame to the new one, and D_{MN}^J is a rotation matrix (Defined in Eq. 2.67 of Landi Degl'Innocenti and Landolfi [2004]).

FIGURE 2.2— Reference frame for the polarization tensor. \mathbf{c} is the direction of propagation, defined by the inclination θ and the azimuth χ . \mathbf{a} , \mathbf{b} are the reference direction of the polarization, defined by the angle γ . More detail in the original figure 5.14 of Landi Degl'Innocenti and Landolfi [2004]

We can express the polarization tensor in terms of spherical tensors as

$$\mathcal{I}_{qq'}(\nu, \mathbf{\Omega}) = \sum_{\alpha\beta=\pm 1} \xi_{qq'}(\alpha, \beta, \mathbf{\Omega}) I_{\beta\alpha}(\nu, \mathbf{\Omega}) = \sum_{i=0}^3 \mathcal{T}_{qq'}(i, \mathbf{\Omega}) S_i(\nu, \mathbf{\Omega}), \quad (2.5)$$

where $\mathcal{T}_{qq'}(\alpha, \beta, \boldsymbol{\Omega})$ (or $\xi_{qq'}$) are the components of a rank 1 (3x3) spherical tensor (see Landi Degl'Innocenti and Landolfi [2004] for further details), and $S_i (i = 0, 1, 2, 3) = \{I, Q, U, V\}$ are the Stokes parameters. By averaging over the solid angle, we define

$$J_{qq'}(\nu) = \oint \frac{d\Omega}{4\pi} \mathcal{T}_{qq'}(\nu, \boldsymbol{\Omega}). \quad (2.6)$$

This is the radiation field tensor and depends on the polarized radiation field propagating in all directions. We now define the irreducible spherical radiation field tensors as

$$\begin{aligned} J_Q^K(\nu) &= \oint \frac{d\Omega}{4\pi} \sum_{qq'} (-1)^{1+q} \sqrt{3(2K+1)} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & K \\ q & -q' & -Q \end{pmatrix} J_{qq'}(\nu) \\ &= \oint \frac{d\Omega}{4\pi} \sum_{i=0}^3 \mathcal{T}_Q^K(i, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) S_i(\nu, \boldsymbol{\Omega}), \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

where $K = \{0, 1, 2\}$, $Q = \{-K, \dots, K\}$, and the quantity between the parenthesis is a $3J$ symbol (see Bolton [1959]). The irreducible spherical tensors transform under the rotation of the reference system as

$$J_Q^K = \sum_{Q'} J_{Q'}^K D_{Q'Q}^K(\alpha, \beta, \gamma), \quad (2.8)$$

where $D_{Q'Q}^K$ is the rotation matrix for the irreducible spherical tensor of rank K .

The irreducible spherical radiation field tensors are described in terms of the Stokes parameters and the irreducible spherical tensors \mathcal{T}_Q^K (see Eq. 2.7). Some components of the $J_Q^K(\nu)$ tensor have a clear and important physical significance, for instance,

$$\begin{aligned} J_0^0 &= \oint \frac{d\Omega}{4\pi} I(\nu, \boldsymbol{\Omega}), \\ J_0^2 &= \oint \frac{d\Omega}{4\pi} \left[\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}} (3 \cos^2 \theta - 1) I(\nu, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{3}{2\sqrt{2}} \cos 2\gamma \sin^2 \theta Q(\nu, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{3}{2\sqrt{2}} \sin 2\gamma \sin^2 \theta U(\nu, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

where θ is the angle between the direction of propagation and the z axis, and γ is the angle between the reference direction of the polarization and the unit vector $\mathbf{d}\theta$ along the direction of propagation (see Fig. 2.2). J_0^0 is the well known mean intensity, which is a measurement of the total energy incoming from all directions. J_0^2 is the anisotropy, related to how the radiation is distributed in θ . A single unpolarized beam propagating parallel to the z direction has $J_0^2 = I/\sqrt{2}$, and an axially symmetric unpolarized radiation field contained in the plane perpendicular to z has $J_0^2 = -I/(2\sqrt{2})$. $J_{Q \neq 0}^K$ indicates the breaking of the axial symmetry of the radiation field, and an axially symmetric radiation field (independent of χ , see Fig. 2.2) has $J_{Q \neq 0}^K = 0$. These tensors are extremely helpful to describe the radiation field and the radiation–matter interaction, as will be evident in section 2.3.

2.2 Atomic density matrix

In the solar atmosphere, the plasma is composed of atoms (neutrals or ions), molecules, and electrons, with the most abundant elements being hydrogen and helium. The radiation field interacts with the matter through the excitation, ionization, recombination, and scattering with atoms, electrons, and molecules. Among all the particles in the plasma, the ones that provide the most information useful for physical diagnosis are the atoms (ions, neutrals, and molecules), which produce the emission and absorption lines that we observe in the solar spectrum.

Quantum theory describes the atom as a combination of discretized energy levels, each one with a given probability of occupation and described by a set of quantum numbers. The fundamental quantum numbers are the following: principal quantum number, n , that describes the level of the principal electron shell, the orbital quantum number, l , that describes the angular momentum of the electron, the magnetic quantum number, m , that describes the projection of the angular momentum on the quantization axis, that we choose to be in the z direction, and the spin quantum number, s , which is a measure of the intrinsic angular momentum of the electron. For a complex atom (with more than one electron) we need to combine the quantum numbers of each electron to describe the atomic state. In this work we use the Russell-Saunders or $L - S$ coupling scheme, adding the electrons orbital angular momenta to form a total orbital angular momentum L and, likewise, the spin of the electrons are combined to form a total spin S . Under the $L - S$ coupling scheme, we use as quantum numbers the total angular momentum J (which is the sum of the total orbital angular momentum L and the total spin S), and the projection of the total angular momentum on the quantization axis (z direction) M , to describe the

atomic state. We end up with a set of quantum numbers describing the atomic state that can be expressed as $|\beta LSJM\rangle$, where β describes the particular electronic configuration of the atomic state.

The excitation state of the atom is then described by the occupation of the atomic states. The occupation of those atomic states depends on the thermodynamic properties of the medium, the radiation field, and the magnetic field. Under local thermodynamic equilibrium conditions (LTE) the excitation state can easily be described by the Saha-Boltzmann equations but, in general, when the medium (or the excitation) is not isotropic (i.e. the radiation field is not isotropic, the medium has non-isotropic collisions, etc.) the occupation of the atomic levels depends on the radiation field and the occupation of the magnetic sublevels is not, in general, uniform. We can describe that occupation state with the density matrix

$$\rho_{\beta LS}(JM, J'M') = \langle \beta LSJM | \hat{\rho} | \beta LSJ'M' \rangle. \quad (2.10)$$

We have used the bra-ket notation to express the density matrix as the expected value of the occupation of the magnetic sublevels. The density matrix is Hermitian ($\rho_{nm} = \rho_{mn}^*$) and semidefinite positive, where the diagonal elements correspond to the occupation of the magnetic sublevels and the off-diagonal elements to the coherence between magnetic sublevels. The density matrix depends on the quantization axis that defines the J_z operator (the projection of the total angular momentum on the quantization axis z).

We can describe the density matrix as an irreducible spherical tensor, which can be easily rotated (analogously to the radiation field tensors, see Eq. 2.8),

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_Q^K(J, J') &= \sum_{mm'} C_J^j(\beta LS, m) C_{J'}^{j'}(\beta LS, m') \\ &\times (-1)^{J-m} \sqrt{2K+1} \begin{pmatrix} J & J' & K \\ m & -m' & -Q \end{pmatrix} \\ &\times \rho_{\beta LS}(jm, j'm'), \end{aligned} \quad (2.11)$$

where $K = \{|J - J'|, |J - J'| + 1, \dots, J + J'\}$, $Q = \{-K, \dots, K\}$ and C_J^j are the Clebsh-Gordan coefficients. If we consider the physical meaning of the different multipole moments of the density matrix, we can see that the ρ_0^0 component is related to the total population of the atomic level, $n_J = \sqrt{2J+1} \rho_0^0(J, J)$. The ρ_0^2 is the alignment (analogous to the anisotropy of the radiation field) and is related to the occupation imbalances between the magnetic sublevels with

different m . The $\rho_{Q \neq 0}^K$ components are called coherences, and are a linear combination of coherences between states characterized by the angular momentum projection (M) differing by Q .

2.3 Interaction between radiation and matter

Once we have described the radiation field (see section 2.1) and the atomic state (see section 2.2), we can describe their interaction. The changes in energy and polarization state of the radiation in its propagation through the medium, which depend on the atomic state, is described by the radiative transfer equations (RTE). The temporal evolution of the atomic state, which depends on the radiation field, is described by the statistical equilibrium equations (SEE). Both systems of equations are coupled and the resulting problem is, in general, non-linear and non-local. Because of that, we need to solve them jointly.

2.3.1 Statistical equilibrium equations

The Statistical Equilibrium Equations (SEE) describe the evolution of an atom's density matrix when interacting with a radiation field, under the influence of both a magnetic field and collisions with other particles in the medium. This system of equations is derived from the time-dependent Schrödinger equation, utilizing both the atom's Hamiltonian and the Hamiltonian of its interaction with the radiation field. This approach primarily considers radiative processes, neglecting other processes such as collisions (for further details, see chapter 6 of Landi Degl'Innocenti and Landolfi [2004]). Nevertheless, radiative processes dominate the scenarios addressed in this thesis. Essentially, the SEE are the evolution equations for the elements of the density matrix. When accounting for bound-bound transitions and the magnetic field, the SEE can be expressed, with the notation $\rho_{mm'} = \langle \beta L S j m | \hat{\rho} | \beta L S j' m' \rangle$, as

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d}{dt}\rho_{mm'} = & -2\pi i\nu_{mm'}\rho_{mm'} + \sum_{nn'}\rho_{nn'}\mathbb{T}_A(m, m', n, n') \\
& + \sum_{pp'}\rho_{pp'}\mathbb{T}_E(m, m', p, p') + \sum_{pp'}\rho_{pp'}\mathbb{T}_S(m, m', p, p') \\
& - \sum_{m''}[\rho_{mm''}\mathbb{R}_A(m, m', m'') + \rho_{m''m'}\mathbb{R}_A(m', m'', m)] \\
& - \sum_{m''}[\rho_{mm''}\mathbb{R}_E(m'', m, m') + \rho_{m''m'}\mathbb{R}_E(m, m', m'')] \\
& - \sum_{m''}[\rho_{mm''}\mathbb{R}_S(m'', m, m') + \rho_{m''m'}\mathbb{R}_S(m, m', m'')] = 0,
\end{aligned} \tag{2.12}$$

where the first term is related to the magnetic field, and the rest are related to the transfer ($\mathbb{T}_{\{A,E,S\}}$) and relaxation ($\mathbb{R}_{\{A,E,S\}}$) rates. In the magnetic field term, $\nu_{mm'}$ is the Larmor frequency of the transition between the magnetic sublevels m and m' , which depends linearly on the magnetic field strength. In the transfer and relaxation rates, the subscripts A , E , and S stand for absorption, spontaneous emission, and stimulated emission, respectively, which all depend on the atomic state and the absorption and stimulated emission also in the radiation field. A schematic representation of these radiative processes is shown in Fig. 2.3.

FIGURE 2.3— Schematic representation of the radiative processes contributing to the SEE. The straight lines represent spontaneous transitions, and the wavy lines represent processes induced by the radiation field (absorption, and stimulated emission).

There are a few implicit assumptions in Eq. (2.12). First, as mentioned before, collisional processes are neglected (for the cases of interest in this thesis, the SEE are dominated by radiative processes). Second, we consider that the characteristic time of the atomic state is much shorter than the characteristic

time for changes in the magnetic or radiation fields, so for solving the equation we can assume that the atomic state is in equilibrium with the radiation field and $\frac{d}{dt}\rho_{mm'} = 0$. Third, we assume the dipole approximation for the Hamiltonian interaction operator.

Adding the following assumptions: the nuclear spin is 0 (atom without hyperfine structure). The atom is described by the L–S coupling scheme, where the quantum numbers L (total angular momentum) and S (total spin) are good quantum numbers, and an eigenvector of the Hamiltonian can be written as $|\beta LSjM\rangle$. This way, different J -levels can be grouped in terms. Lastly, coherence between J -levels pertaining to different terms are negligible.

then the SEE can be written in the irreducible spherical tensor representation as

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d}{dt}\beta LS\rho_Q^K(J, J') &= -2\pi i \sum_{K'Q'} \sum_{J''J'''} N_{\beta LS}(KQJJ', K'Q'J''J''') \beta LS\rho_{Q'}^{K'}(J'', J''') \\
&+ \sum_{\beta_\ell L_\ell K_\ell Q_\ell J_\ell J'_\ell} \beta_\ell L_\ell S \rho_{Q_\ell}^{K_\ell}(J_\ell, J'_\ell) \mathbb{T}_A(\beta LSKQJJ', \beta_\ell L_\ell SK_\ell Q_\ell J_\ell J'_\ell) \\
&+ \sum_{\beta_u L_u K_u Q_u J_u J'_u} \beta_u L_u S \rho_{Q_u}^{K_u}(J_u, J'_u) [\mathbb{T}_E(\beta LSKQJJ', \beta_u L_u SK_u Q_u J_u J'_u) \\
&\quad + \mathbb{T}_S(\beta LSKQJJ', \beta_u L_u SK_u Q_u J_u J'_u)] \\
&- \sum_{K'Q'J''J'''} \beta LS\rho_{Q'}^{K'}(J'', J''') [\mathbb{R}_A(\beta LSKQJJ'K'Q'J''J''') \\
&\quad + \mathbb{R}_E(\beta LSKQJJ'K'Q'J''J''') \\
&\quad + \mathbb{R}_S(\beta LSKQJJ'K'Q'J''J''')] = 0,
\end{aligned} \tag{2.13}$$

where the subindex ℓ stands for a lower term (in energy) with respect to the βLS term, and the subindex u for an upper energy term. This equation describes the evolution of the density matrix element $\beta LS\rho_Q^K(J, J')$. This particular SEE is usually dubbed the multi-term atom model. The exact formulation of the transfer and relaxation rates can be found in Eq. (7.34) of Landi Degl'Innocenti and Landolfi [2004]. These equations assume that the incident radiation spectrum is flat in a frequency range given by the frequency separation between different levels belonging to the same term. In practice, this flat-spectrum condition is fulfilled by introducing in the transfer rates an average in frequency of the radiation field tensors, weighted by the absorption profile

$$\bar{J}_Q^K = \int \phi(\nu) J_Q^K(\nu) d\nu, \quad (2.14)$$

where $\phi(\nu)$ is the line profile function which, in most cases, is a *voigt* profile, although here, in the multi-term case, it is the normalized absorption profile. In fact, in the case of the multi-term atom, the absorption profile of a term includes all the profiles of the transitions in the term.

2.3.2 Radiative transfer equations (RTE)

When the radiation propagates through a medium, it can be absorbed, emitted, and scattered. These processes change the intensity and the polarization state of the radiation. The change that the Stokes parameters experiment when travelling a distance ds in a particular direction $\mathbf{\Omega}$, is described by the radiative transfer equation (RTE) as

$$\frac{d\mathbf{I}}{ds} = -\hat{K}\mathbf{I} + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}, \quad (2.15)$$

where $\mathbf{I} = \{I, Q, U, V\}$ is the Stokes vector, \hat{K} is the propagation matrix, and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \{\epsilon_I, \epsilon_Q, \epsilon_U, \epsilon_V\}$ is the emission vector (note that all quantities depend on the frequency ν , the propagation direction $\mathbf{\Omega}$, and the position \mathbf{r}). The propagation matrix describes the absorption and stimulated emission processes, and the emission vector describes the spontaneous emission process. The propagation matrix can be expressed as

$$\hat{K} = \hat{K}^{(a)} - \hat{K}^{(s)} = \begin{pmatrix} \eta_I & \eta_Q & \eta_U & \eta_V \\ \eta_Q & \eta_I & \rho_V & -\rho_U \\ \eta_U & -\rho_V & \eta_I & \rho_Q \\ \eta_V & \rho_U & -\rho_Q & \eta_I \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.16)$$

The quantities η_i account for the extinction, and the ρ_i for the dispersion. The propagation matrix and the emission vector are a function of the atomic state, and the exact form of the ρ_i , η_i , and ϵ_i depend on the type of atomic model, i.e., the set of assumptions introduced in the solution of the Hamiltonian (multi-level, multi-term, etc.). For the multi-term atom in the irreducible spherical basis, the ρ_i and η_i are given by Eq. (7.35) in Landi Degl'Innocenti and Landolfi [2004].

In this thesis, we assume complete frequency redistribution (CRD), i.e., that the absorbed and emitted radiation is completely uncorrelated. This implies that we only take into account absorption and emission processes (which are 1st order processes), and neglect scattering (which are a 2nd order process).

This approximation is valid for the lines that will be studied in this thesis (He I 10830 Å multiplet, see Asensio Ramos et al. [2008]; Ca II 8542 Å line, see Uitenbroek [1989]). Under the CRD approximation, for a given density matrix, the RTE equations for different frequencies and directions are decoupled. By defining the optical depth as $d\tau = -\eta_I ds$, Eq. (2.15) can be rewritten as

$$\frac{d\mathbf{I}}{d\tau} = \hat{K}' \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{S}, \quad (2.17)$$

where $\mathbf{S} = \epsilon_i/\eta_I$ is the source function, and $\hat{K}' = \mathbf{K}/\eta_I$. Eq. (2.17) has the formal solution at the point O

$$\mathbf{I}_O(\nu) = \mathbf{O}(\nu, \Delta\tau_M)\mathbf{I}_M(\nu) + \int_0^{\Delta\tau_M} \mathbf{O}(\nu, t)S(t)dt, \quad (2.18)$$

where $\mathbf{O}(0, \Delta\tau_M)$ is the evolution operator (i.e. the 4x4 Mueller matrix of the atmospheric slab between t and $\Delta\tau_M$, see Trujillo Bueno [2003]). Equation 2.18 relates \mathbf{I}_O in a particular point O with the \mathbf{I}_M in a previous point of the propagation M .

Eq. (2.18), in general, does not have an analytical solution, and has to be solved numerically. To solve this equation we make use of the short characteristics method, discretizing the ray path in points M , O , and P and assuming a functional form of the source function along the path. Thus, I , Q , U , and V at point O are given by

$$\mathbf{I}_O = \mathbf{O}(\nu, \Delta\tau_M)\mathbf{I}_M + \Psi_M\mathbf{S}_M + \Psi_O\mathbf{S}_O + \Psi_P\mathbf{S}_P, \quad (2.19)$$

where Ψ_i with $i = M, O, \text{ and } P$ are 4×4 matrices which depend on the optical distance between M and O , and between O and P . They depend on the functional form assumed for the source function. Figure 2.3.2 shows a schematic representation of the method of short characteristics.

Given the boundary conditions, we can find the Stokes parameters at any given point, in any given direction and frequency, by computing the Stokes parameters in steps along the propagation path.

2.3.3 Matter-Radiation interaction: The NLTE problem

As it was mentioned in sections 2.3.1 and 2.3.2, the transfer rates $\mathbb{T}_{A,S}$ and $\mathbb{R}_{A,S}$ depend on the radiation field, that are integrals of the Stokes parameters which, in turn, are the solution of the RTE. Likewise, \hat{K} and ϵ depend on the density matrix, which is the solution of the SEE. Consequently, the atomic state and the radiation field are coupled and both systems of equations have to be solved jointly.

FIGURE 2.4— Schematic diagram of the short characteristics method. The radiation goes from the preceding point M to the next point P , passing through the point of interest O . M and P are used to sample the source function and, by assuming its functional form, compute the radiation field at O .

The problem is even more intricate when we consider that the radiation propagates, and therefore is a non-local quantity spatially coupled by the RTE. This makes the global problem both non-linear and non-local. This is the so-called Non-Local Thermodynamic Equilibrium (NLTE) problem of second kind (to distinguish it from the NLTE problem without polarization). The solution of the NLTE problem is also dubbed as forward modelling or forward solution, due to the fact that we are solving the direct problem of retrieving the emergent radiation field from a given set of atmospheric parameters. To actually solve it, we need methods to solve the RTE and the SEE at the same time, accounting for the non-local and non-linear nature of the problem.

Nowadays, this problem is most often solved using iterative methods. In these methods we start from an initial guess for the density matrix (e.g., by assuming LTE) that we use to solve the RTE. The resulting radiation field is used to compute the SEE, obtaining a new density matrix (in general different from the previous one). Then, the process is repeated until the change in the density matrix elements is small enough,³ and a state where the \bar{J}_Q^K and the ρ_Q^K are consistent is reached. This is the simplest iterative method for the NLTE problem, usually dubbed Lambda Iteration.

The Lambda Iteration method is the simplest and more robust method, but its convergence is very slow and there is no certainty that it converges to the correct solution in optically thick regions if the initial guess is very different from the actual solution. To speed things up and to obtain more accurate results,

³Where small enough means that the maximum relative change in the density matrix elements is smaller than a given tolerance.

we need to use alternative and more sophisticated methods, such as the Jacobi method or the Gauss-Seidel method. These methods use the information from the previous iterations to speed up the convergence and are usually dubbed Accelerated Lambda Iteration methods (ALI). An overview of the different methods used to solve the polarized NLTE problem can be found in Janett et al. [2021] and Benedusi et al. [2021].

2.4 The inverse problem

The inverse problem consist in inferring the physical properties of the plasma encoded in the observed spectrum. The inverse problem has as an objective to construct a model of the atmosphere that, when passed through the forward solver, reproduces the observed spectrum. Given the fact that the observations have noise, that the model atmosphere may not include all the relevant physical processes, and that the solution is potentially degenerate, we will never be able to retrieve the exact model atmosphere. The best we can do is to find a compatible model atmosphere that minimizes the difference between the observed and the synthetic spectrum. Therefore, the inverse problem can be seen as an optimization problem, where we try to find the model atmosphere that when passed through the forward solver, gives the best fitting spectrum.

We can formulate the optimization of the inverse problem as follows. We propose a model atmosphere and compute the synthetic spectrum with the forward solver. Once we have a synthetic spectrum we can compare it with the observed one. If they do not match, we compute the numerical derivatives of the forward model with respect to the model atmosphere parameters and change the model atmosphere accordingly until we can minimize the difference between the observed and the synthetic spectrum. A diagram of the forward and inverse problem is shown in Fig. 2.5.

A lot of factors come into play to have a successful inversion. The first one is the choice of the model atmosphere discretization scheme and the model atom. They have to be flexible enough to reproduce the observed spectrum, but not as much as to make the optimization problem computationally unfeasible. Another important factor is the optimization algorithm. Historically, the most used algorithm is the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm (which is a combination of a second order Newton method and a first order gradient descent method), but there are many others. The last factor is the definition of merit or cost function to minimize. It should be a good measure of the difference between the observed and the synthetic spectrum, and ideally the derivatives of the merit function with respect to the model atmosphere parameters should be easy to compute and provide us relevant information. The distance between

FIGURE 2.5— Schematic diagram of the NLTE inversion process. The right side of the Figure shows the inverse problem as an optimization problem. The left side shows the detail of the Forward solver which is part of the inversion.

the synthetic and the observed Stokes profiles is typically measured using the χ^2 metric because the noise is assumed to be Gaussian.

If we take into account that the forward problem by itself is already an iterative process, which can be very time-consuming depending on the complexity of the atomic system, the number of parameters of the model atmosphere, and the amount and complexity of the physical processes under consideration, we can expect the inverse problem to be extremely time-consuming. This is primarily due to the fact that response functions, specifically the elements of the Jacobian matrix, are typically employed to understand how the model reacts to parameter variations. These functions describe the changes in emergent Stokes profiles in response to perturbations in the physical quantities. The response functions are difficult to obtain due to the non-linear and non-local character of the NLTE problem, and arguably the most convenient way of computing them is through numerical evaluation using finite differences. As a consequence, each step of a NLTE inversion requires many solutions of the full NLTE forward solver (one for the synthesis and an additional set for the calculation of response functions using finite differences). Multiplying the number of model atmosphere parameters and the number of iterations required for convergence reveals that the computational complexity of the inverse problem scales poorly.

In some inversion techniques, certain approximations can be made to expedite the process for specific problems. The initial approximation utilized by nearly all codes is the 1D plane-parallel approximation. In this approach, the atmosphere is discretized with the assumption that its physical properties remain constant in the horizontal direction. This simplification ignores both horizontal radiation transfer effects and horizontal gradients of the physical properties. This approximation is very useful to reduce the computational complexity and allows us to invert each pixel independently,⁴ but it presents an important drawback. The 1D plane parallel approximation can be not suitable in the chromosphere, where the horizontal gradients and the radiation transfer in 3D. Another critical approximation commonly used in the analysis of photospheric lines is the assumption of LTE. In LTE the density matrix only depends on the local temperature and the forward problem is linear, so the RTE have to be solved just once for a single propagation direction. Moreover, in LTE the Jacobian matrix has analytical expressions, removing the need for multiple evaluations of the forward solution per inversion iteration altogether. For these reasons, this approximation accelerates the inversion procedure by orders of magnitude. The downside of the LTE approximation is that it is only suitable for spectral lines forming in the deepest layers of the photosphere, where the relatively large density allows for the thermalization of the atoms. Inversion codes like SIR (Ruiz Cobo and del Toro Iniesta [1992]) and SPINOR (Frutiger et al. [2000]) exploit this approximation. To be able to infer the physical properties in the higher layers of the photosphere or in the chromosphere, the LTE approximation needs to be relaxed. The NICOLE code (Socas-Navarro et al. [2000]) approaches this problem by numerically calculating the Jacobian matrix. The more recent SNAP1 code (Milić and van Noort [2018]) approaches the problem by calculating the Jacobian matrix semi-analytically, improving the performance by a factor 2 or 3 with respect to the fully numerical derivatives. The more recent DeSIRe code (Ruiz Cobo et al. [2021]) attempts to exploit the advantages of the analytical calculation of the derivatives by computing them in LTE, but introducing departure coefficients (the ratio between the NLTE and LTE populations) that are only recalculated after several inversion iterations. The FIRTEZ-dz code (Pastor Yabar et al. [2019]) follows a similar approach, but it retrieves the geometrical stratification⁵. The STiC code (de la

⁴In reality, even if the atmosphere was in fact 1D plane parallel, the instrumental effects of the telescopes (like the point spread function) would correlate adjacent pixels and make the inversion of each pixel not completely independent.

⁵Most inversion codes work in optical depth scale assuming hydrostatic equilibrium, due to the lack of an absolute zero for the height scale and the degeneracy between temperature, gas pressure, and density in this scale. by considering the magneto-hydrostatic momentum

Cruz Rodríguez et al. [2019]) follows the fully numerical approach, but relaxing the CRD approximation and including partial frequency redistribution (PRD) effects, opening the window for the diagnosis of strong chromospheric lines for which these effects are critical. Finally, the `HanleRT-TIC` code (del Pino Alemán et al. [2016], Li et al. [2022]) also follows the fully numerical approach accounting for PRD, but it can also account for atomic and scattering polarization and quantum interference, key physical ingredients for the modeling of the linear polarization of strong chromospheric lines.

A special consideration should be made regarding the diagnosis of filaments with the He I triplet lines. The particularities of the formation of these lines (see chapter 4) have allowed the `Hazel` code (Asensio Ramos et al. [2008]) to exploit the optically thin constant property slab approximation while accounting for NLTE effects and scattering polarization. The suitability of the CRD approximation for these lines makes the `Hazel` code very fast when compared with full NLTE radiation transfer codes, and it has thus become the main tool for the analysis of spectro-polarimetric data of filaments.

Of course, the more physical effect are included, the more computationally demanding the inversion is. Inversion codes using the LTE or the constant property slab approximations can perform an inversion of a pixel in seconds. In contrast, inversion codes accounting for NLTE effects with full radiation transfer require significantly longer inversion times, ranging from minutes to even hours. This increased processing time presents a significant challenge when attempting to invert large fields of view (FOV) or when real-time inversions are desirable.

In this thesis we tackle two of the issues that can be gathered from the limitations of the available inversion tools. First, there is a strong push for the possibility of performing NLTE inversions with a computational cost similar to that of LTE inversions. In chapter 3 we describe an approach based on machine learning that speeds-up the inversion of chromospheric lines such as the Ca I line at 8542 Å by a factor of 1000. Second, the 1D approximation could not be suitable, specially when accounting for scattering polarization. In the framework of this thesis we have developed a 3D inversion code capable of relaxing this approximation. We describe this code, dubbed POLARIS, in chapter 5, and we show an application to a spectro-polarimetric observation of a prominence in chapter 6.

equation in ideal magneto-hydrodynamics.

3

Accelerating NLTE inversions with GNN

All models are wrong, but some are useful.

George E. P. Box.

(Journal of the American Statistical Association 1976)

In contrast with the large computational requirements of NLTE synthesis/inversion codes discussed in chapter 2, when the LTE approximation is suitable the inversion is much simpler and significantly faster to perform. Given this difference in speed, one would ideally like to have a NLTE inversion code that performs as fast as an LTE code. This search for faster codes is motivated by the fact that current telescopes routinely produce spectropolarimetric observations with fields of view (FOV) of the order of megapixels, in many cases with high temporal cadence. The time-consuming NLTE inversion codes are routinely only applied to small regions of the FOV, and even for these a significant amount of CPU time is needed.

From a theoretical point of view, a fast NLTE inversion code could be achieved if one could have access, through an “instantaneous” computation, to the so-called departure coefficients, the ratio between the self-consistent NLTE populations and those calculated by assuming LTE. The knowledge of these coefficients would allow for bypassing the iterative solution of the NLTE problem, which is the most time-consuming part of the NLTE inversion codes. A similar motivation is behind the DeSIRE code (Ruiz Cobo et al. [2021]), which also uses the departure coefficients and the LTE populations to speed up the

solution of the NLTE problem, but without the use of machine learning.

In this chapter, we propose a new type of approach in the form of a trained graph neural network (GNN, Battaglia et al. [2018]). The network takes as input the depth stratification of the physical conditions (temperature, gas pressure, line of sight velocity, and microturbulent velocity) on an arbitrary 1D grid and outputs the departure coefficients for a selection of atoms. The GNN is fast and differentiable, so it can be used in combination with an LTE-like inversion code to carry out fast NLTE inversions. This opens the possibility of quickly getting chromospheric information from large FOVs. In this chapter, we motivate the use of machine learning (and in particular the use of GNNs) for the solution of the NLTE problem (section 3.1). We then describe the implementation of the problem (section 3.2), including the creation of the dataset, the optimization of the network, and the integration with the HAZEL2 inversion code. We then describe the validation process of the network (Section 3.3) and, finally, we show the results of an application to real data as well as the performance of the network in comparison with traditional methods (Section 3.4).

3.1 Introduction to machine learning

Machine learning (ML) has become a powerful tool in the solution of diverse problems in science and also in astrophysics. From the analysis of large data sets, constructing complex models when we do not have a clear understanding of the underlying physics, to even giving an approximate, albeit fast, solution to problems that would be computationally intractable otherwise.

The main idea behind ML is to use an algorithm that can learn patterns from a set of data and then generalize this knowledge to make predictions on new data or, in other words, to learn a non-linear function from the data. The most common type of ML algorithms are supervised learning algorithms, where the algorithm learns the mapping between a set of input-output pairs.

Various types of algorithms are employed depending on the specific problem, such as regression, classification, clustering, and others. In this thesis we will focus on the use of neural networks, which are a type of ML algorithm inspired by how the human brain works. The building block of a neural network is the perceptron, which is a simple model of a neuron that takes a set of inputs, applies a series of weights and biases to them, and passes the result through a non-linear activation function. The perceptrons are connected in parallel in layers, and the layers are stacked to form a neural network, where the output of one layer is the input of the next one. The neural network is trained by adjusting the weights and biases of the perceptrons to minimize a loss function

that measures the difference between the predicted output and the true output.

The fully connected neural networks (FCNN) use a combination of perceptrons, containing a series of learnable weights and biases, to approximate a function or process through a carefully designed architecture (see, e.g., Chollet [2017]). The basic building block of a perceptron is the neuron and can be described as

$$\mathbf{a}^L = \sigma(\mathbf{W}\mathbf{a}^{L-1} + \mathbf{b}^{L-1}), \quad (3.1)$$

where \mathbf{a}^{L-1} and \mathbf{a}^L are the input from a previous layer and the output vector of the neuron at layer L , respectively. The neuron applies a matrix of weights, \mathbf{W} , to the input, adds a bias, \mathbf{b}^{L-1} , and then passes the result through a nonlinear activation function σ . The dimensions of \mathbf{a}^{L-1} and \mathbf{a}^L can be different depending on the size of the layers $L-1$ and L respectively, so in general we have: $\mathbf{a}^L \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $\mathbf{a}^{L-1} \in \mathbb{R}^m$, $\mathbf{b}^{L-1} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$, and $\sigma: \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$.

Our objective is to define and train a neural network that can quickly provide the departure coefficients for all the levels of the atoms of interest at every point in the grid atmosphere. The architecture of the neural network has to fulfill some properties to be of practical use. First, it needs to be fast. This is trivially fulfilled by almost any architecture when compared with the typical computing time needed to solve the NLTE problem. Second, it needs to be flexible, so it can be applied to arbitrary atmospheric grids. Third, it needs to take into account that the NLTE problem is non-local and non-linear. Therefore, the possible correlation between the information from far apart grid points needs to be properly considered. An architecture that fulfills all these properties are the recently developed Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) of Battaglia et al. [2018].

The fundamental idea consists in viewing the atmosphere as a grid (1D, 2D, or 3D) and convert it to a connected graph $G = (V, E)$, where V is the set of grid points (also known as nodes or vertices) and E is the set of edges connecting the grid points. This allows for the application of graph networks to an arbitrary number of grid points, placed at arbitrary locations (so it can easily work with non-cartesian atmospheres in multiple dimensions). Each node represents the set of relevant physical properties $\mathbf{p}_i \in V$ at each location of the atmosphere. Each edge $\mathbf{e}_{ij} \in E$ connects two nodes, the sender i and the receiver j , and describes relevant inter-node properties.

A schematic representation of all the processing involved in a graph network, as defined by Battaglia et al. [2018], is shown in Fig. 3.1. The physical representation displays how a one-dimensional model atmosphere (the vectors of parameters that can describe the solar atmosphere, i.e., B, T, ρ, \dots) is transformed into a connected graph. Nodes encode physical properties p_i and edges

encode internode information. The second step is to project the properties of the nodes and edges to a latent space of higher dimension with the aid of two fully connected neural encoders. This projection increases the dimensionality of the information encoded in nodes and edges, allowing the network to describe more complex relationships, which largely increases the information encoding capabilities of the graph network. For simplicity, we use the same dimensionality for both variables. The resulting graph is shown in the latent representation, where nodes and edges are labeled with their corresponding latent variables.

The architecture of the GNN used in this study is particularly well-suited for addressing the NLTE problem due to its capability to capture both the non-local and non-linear characteristics inherent to the problem. Each message passing step, fundamental to the GNN, updates the information of adjacent nodes in a way that reminds of the solution of the RTE. This process transforms the information based on the properties encoded in each node, passing it along to the next and effectively combining information across the entire atmospheric grid. As described by Battaglia et al. [2018], the core of the graph network lies in the processor part, which consists of N consecutive message passing processes. Each message passing step involves updating the latent information contained in all edges and nodes. At each iteration t , the edge update phase employs a FCNN, f_E^t , to modify the encoded information. This neural network takes as input the concatenation of the edge and the nodes it connects, producing a modified output through an additional residual connection (He et al. [2016]),

$$\mathbf{e}_{ij}^t = \mathbf{e}_{ij}^{t-1} + f_E^t(\mathbf{e}_{ij}^{t-1}, \mathbf{v}_i^{t-1}, \mathbf{v}_j^{t-1}). \quad (3.2)$$

This very same neural network is applied to all edges (it can be done in parallel) but it is different for each iteration of the message passing.

The node update step modifies the node latent information by using a couple of FCNNs, f_A^t and f_V^t . The first one is used to compute an effective edge information for each node. In general, we use

$$\bar{\mathbf{e}}_j^t = \sum_k f_A^t(\mathbf{v}_k^{t-1}, \mathbf{e}_{kj}^t), \quad (3.3)$$

where the summation is carried out over all edges k for which the node j is a receiver. A simpler form of this equation, which we use in practice and also gives good results (Sánchez-González et al. [2020]), is to use the average instead of the summation, what also reduces gradient explosion.¹ Spatial invariance is

¹Gradient explosion refers to the phenomenon where gradients grow exponentially during backpropagation (training/fitting process), leading to unstable updates in neural network parameters and complicating the training process.

FIGURE 3.1— Schematic representation of the graph networks used to predict the departure coefficients. The quantities marked in blue in the processor phase are the ones being updated.

introduced as an additional inductive bias, something that can be of interest in case one wants this symmetry of optical depth between nodes to be conserved (Battaglia et al. [2018]). Finally, the value of the node is updated following:

$$\mathbf{v}_j^t = f_V^t(\mathbf{v}_j^{t-1}, \mathbf{e}_j^t). \quad (3.4)$$

Note that the encoding, decoding, node, and edge update functions are FCNN, which take as inputs the physical quantities, node and/or edge values and connect them to the desired output. Also note that the nodes at the extremes of the graph have only one edge.

Message passing is fundamental to connect the information in very distant nodes in the graph. For simplicity, we only consider edges that connect consecutive nodes. Given that all updates are local (and can therefore be carried out in parallel), a simple reasoning shows that $\sim N_p$ iterations are needed to connect the information in all nodes in our simple graph topology. The results show that this is a good topology election, although the number of message passing iterations could be potentially reduced if we use a more complex connectivity, where each node is connected to the nearest k neighbors. This would come at the cost of greater memory requirements due to the increased number of edges.

A final decoder projects the values of the latent space in the nodes to the desired output. In our case, we predict the departure coefficients for the N_L levels of interest. This projection is again done in parallel for all nodes in the graph.

3.2 Implementation of the problem

The main idea behind our GNN is to bypass the solution of the NLTE problem, which is the most time-consuming part in NLTE inversions. Once knowing how a GNN works, we can see that the problem of predicting the departure coefficients can be easily implemented in this framework. In this section we will describe how the equations of chapter 2 can be written in terms of the departure coefficients (section 3.2.1), how to create the data set needed for the training of the network, what data we need to encode in the nodes and edges of the network (section 3.2.2), and how we have optimized the network (section 3.2.3).

3.2.1 Bypassing the NLTE problem with GNN

The core idea behind bypassing the NLTE problem with the GNN is to use the departure coefficients to speed up the solution. The departure coefficient of an atomic level is defined as the ratio between its populations in NLTE and

in LTE. If the total population of an arbitrary level k with angular momentum J is $n_k = \sqrt{2J+1}\rho_0^0(k)$, its departure coefficients is:

$$b_k = \frac{n_k}{n_k^*}, \quad (3.5)$$

where n_k^* is the population of level k in LTE. This LTE population can be easily obtained from the Saha-Boltzmann equation (Saha [1921]) which only depends on local quantities. The RTE can be written in terms of departure coefficients and LTE populations. From equation (2.17), the source function is defined as the ratio

$$\mathbf{S} = \frac{\epsilon}{\eta_I}, \quad (3.6)$$

where, as in chapter 2, η_I is the line opacity. We remind the reader that all quantities in Eq. (3.6) depend on the frequency, position, and propagation direction.

In this particular application, we deliberately neglect atomic polarization to simplify the problem. For our purpose, the previous equations can be more conveniently rewritten in terms of the departure coefficients. For instance, the opacity for a bound-bound transition can be rewritten in terms of the departure coefficients as

$$\eta_I = \frac{h\nu}{4\pi} b_l n_l^* \phi_\nu \left(1 - \frac{b_u}{b_l} e^{-h\nu/kT} \right), \quad (3.7)$$

and the corresponding line source function as

$$S = \frac{2h\nu_0^3}{c^2} \frac{1}{\frac{b_l}{b_u} e^{h\nu/kT} - 1} \frac{\phi_\eta}{\phi_\epsilon}, \quad (3.8)$$

where ν_0 is the central frequency of the transition, ϕ_η is the normalized line absorption profile, and ϕ_ϵ is the normalized line emission profile (both dependent on the frequency, and equal under the CRD approximation when $B = 0$). Once we have obtained the opacity and the source function in terms of the departure coefficients, and those coefficients through the GNN, and as previously stated, the LTE populations from the Saha-Boltzmann equation, we can bypass the solution of the NLTE problem. Effectively, it is enough to just solve the RTE for a single line of sight (LOS) to obtain the emergent intensity.

To implement the GNN we decided to encode in the nodes the temperature, T , in K, the optical depth measured at 500 nm, $\tau_{500} = \int \chi_{500} ds$, the electron number density, n_e , in m^{-3} , the microturbulent velocity, v_{mic} , in $\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, and the line of sight velocity, v_{LOS} , in $\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. We use the logarithm of all the quantities,

except for the velocities, to better capture their variability in order of magnitude. The selection of these five variables has given very good results as we show in section 3.4. However, there are no fundamental constraints preventing the inclusion of additional variables if required. For example, the presence of strong magnetic fields would significantly influence the RT coefficients through their impact in the populations. For the edges we use the optical distance measured at 500 nm between the nodes as the encoded information. With this selection, $\mathbf{e}_{ij} = -\mathbf{e}_{ji}$, but the formalism is general and can seamlessly deal with asymmetric edge properties.

We point out that there is a certain degree of overlap on the information encoded in the nodes and edges because the optical depth is encoded in both. However, given the enormous variability in the optical depth axes for the models that we consider for training and validation, we found that encoding its absolute value in the nodes gave better generalization properties. We defer for the future potential simplifications of the node encoding to reduce the overlap.

3.2.2 Building the training data set

To train the GNN, as we mentioned in the previous section, we need a set of input-output pairs. The inputs are the physical properties of the model atmosphere represented in the nodes and edges of the graph, and the outputs are the departure coefficients at the same grid points for the atomic levels of interest. To construct these pairs, we need to solve the NLTE problem for a set of model atmospheres. We performed these calculations with the Lightweaver framework (Osborne and Milić [2021]). Given the time consuming solution of the NLTE forward problem, the ease of use of the Lightweaver framework facilitates the deployment of the generation of the training set in a parallel machine. Although the method is general, we focus here on results for Ca II whose lines are widely used to infer the properties of the chromosphere (e.g., Lites et al. [1999], Quintero Noda et al. [2016], Štěpán and Trujillo Bueno [2016]). The Ca II infrared triplet is routinely used to extract quantitative information from the lower- to mid-chromosphere, given that plenty of observations are available. In this work we make use of observations performed with the CRISP instrument (Scharmer et al. [2008]) mounted on the Swedish 1-m Solar Telescope (Scharmer et al. [2003], Scharmer [2006]).

The model atom that we use is part of the Lightweaver distribution. We use a simple atomic model that contains the five bounded energy levels $4s^2S_{1/2}$, $4p^2P_{1/2}$, $4p^2P_{3/2}$, $3d^2D_{3/2}$, and $3d^2D_{5/2}$, responsible for the Ca II infrared triplet and the H & K lines in the blue part of the spectrum. We also include the Ca III ground term to take into account the bound-free transitions.

The infrared triplet lines are treated in CRD, while the H & K lines are treated in PRD. It is worth noticing that the CRD and PRD cases have different complexity in terms of the solution of the NLTE problem. However, due to the large flexibility and fitting power of the GNN we do not need to adapt the basic procedure, except perhaps increasing the complexity of the GNN by using larger neural networks in cases in which the error with respect to the true value is unacceptably large.

All calculations are made under the field-free simplifying approximation for the sake of clarity, but it can be lifted if needed without fundamentally affecting the procedure. This approximation assumes that the solution of the SEE is unaffected by the presence of Zeeman splitting in the energy levels (Rees [1969]). If the magnetic field is large enough (in the order of tens of kG for the Ca II line at 8542 Å), one should add its effect on the SEE. In this case, apart from increasing the computation time for the generation of the database, one would probably need to add the magnetic field strength (and potentially its orientation) as a new parameter in the nodes of the GNN.

For the sake of producing a GNN that properly generalizes to new unseen models, we put some emphasis on generating a database of atmospheric models with significant excursions on all the physical properties. To this end, we use the semi-empirical A, C, F, and XCO models of Fontenla et al. [1993] and Avrett and Loeser [2008] as baselines and add perturbations in the temperature, microturbulent velocity, and line-of-sight velocity. We use signed Gaussian random perturbations. In the case of the temperature we used a standard deviation of 2500 K, for the microturbulent velocities the standard deviation was a relative perturbation of 20, and for the LOS velocities $2.5 \text{ km}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. All these perturbations are realized at nodes located at $\log \tau_{500} = -5, -4, -3, -2, -1$ and 0. Prior to adding them to the underlying model, these perturbations are adequately interpolated and smoothed to avoid very strong gradients that might compromise the convergence of the non-LTE problem. Since we have perturbed the temperature, the electron density of the model is not consistent anymore. For this reason, the electron pressure is computed for these models assuming hydrostatic equilibrium. To this set of randomized models, we add models extracted from the snapshot at $t = 3850 \text{ s}$ of the enhanced network simulation of Carlsson et al. [2016], computed with the Bifrost code (Gudiksen et al. [2011]). The microturbulent velocity of these models is set to zero. A total of 70.000 models have been produced in three data sets. One data set contains 50.000 of those models, which are actually used during training, while the remaining 20.000 are used as validation and test sets to tune the hyperparameters and check for overfitting and generalization. The full NLTE problem for Ca II is

solved in each model atmosphere with Lightweaver using the MALI method with full preconditioning (Osborne and Milić [2021]), similarly to the RH code (Uitenbroek [2001]). The process is run in a distributed machine with 60 cores and takes ~ 16 h.

3.2.3 Optimization

The optimization is the process of adjusting the parameters of a model, the GNN, to minimize the error between the predicted and the true output. However, there are a few hyperparameters that need to be defined a priori. The most important ones are the size of the latent space used by the encoders (i.e., the dimension of vectors v_i and e_{ij}), the number of message passing iterations, and the specific architecture of all FCNN. We carried out a systematic parametric study and found some values that seem optimal. The size of the latent space is set to 64. All neural networks, i.e., the encoder, the decoder, f_V^t , f_A^t , and f_E^t , contain two hidden layers of size 64 with an ELU activation function (Clevert et al. [2016]). Concerning the number of message passing steps, we find a significant increase in precision when more message passing steps are used, albeit with a significant increase in memory consumption. For this reason, and because the degree of improvement slows down significantly with more steps, we find a balance by setting the number of message passing steps to 100.

The neural networks are coded in PyTorch (Paszke et al. [2019]), using the PyTorch Geometric package (Fey and Lenssen [2019]) for neural networks in graphs. We use the Adam optimizer (Kingma and Ba [2014]) with a learning rate of 10^{-4} , which is annealed at each epoch using a cosine rule. The training is done by optimizing the mean squared error (MSE) between the predicted and computed departure coefficients in logarithmic scale. We use a logarithm scale because the departure coefficients are spread over several orders of magnitude. The number of total trainable parameters is ~ 5.5 M. We train for 400 epochs on an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080Ti, for a total of 52 h. Due to GPU memory constrains (12 GB), the batch size was limited to 32-64.

3.3 Validation

Once trained, we checked the generalization properties of the GNN, which is fundamental in any approach based on machine learning. To this end, we utilize the snapshot at $t = 5300$ s from the Bifrost simulation. This snapshot is extracted 24 min after the one used for training. This time is a few times larger than the typical lifetime of a granule, so the new snapshot can be considered to be sufficiently uncorrelated with the one used for training. We solve the NLTE problem in all columns of this new snapshot and compare the results with those

of the neural prediction. After training, our baseline GNN displays an average MSE loss computed over this test dataset of 10^{-4} . Though this points out to a good generalization capabilities of the GNN, we analyze the results in more detail in the ongoing sections.

3.3.1 Departure coefficients

The first test is to directly compare the result of the network with its desired output, i.e., the departure coefficients computed with the NLTE code. Figure 3.2 displays the probability distribution of the relative difference between the computed departure coefficient and the one predicted by the GNN for all the atomic levels considered in the Ca II model in a random subsample of 5.000 pixels. The legend also displays the percentage of pixels in the simulation with a relative error below 1% and 5%, respectively. The distributions are very peaky (note that they are displayed in logarithmic scale), with a relatively Gaussian central core and extended wings. These distributions clearly show the generalization capabilities of the GNN, giving predicted departure coefficients of significant precision in unseen data.

FIGURE 3.2— Gaussian kernel density estimation of the relative error between the correct departure coefficient and the one predicted by our neural approach for all energy levels considered in the Ca II model. The legend shows the percentage of cases for which b/b_{NN} are in the intervals $[-0.01, 0.01]$ and $[-0.05, 0.05]$, respectively.

This distribution is affected by the fact that the departure coefficients in the

deeper zones of the atmosphere are very close to unity, which our GNN predicts very well. Only a small fraction of all available heights really contribute to the formation of the Ca II lines.

In order to better display this behavior, Fig. 3.3 shows the distribution of relative errors as a function of geometrical height in the 3D snapshot. The solid blue line shows the median, while the shaded blue and orange areas denote the $\pm 68\%$ and $\pm 95\%$ percentiles, respectively. It is clear that our prediction for the deeper regions is always very good since all levels are in LTE. The quality of the prediction decreases with height, reaching relative differences larger than 15% in the upper part of the snapshot. These heights correspond to the base of the corona or the upper part of the transition region, depending on the selected pixel, but they are not important for the formation of the Ca II lines. For the regions where the lines are formed, we find relative errors that are safely below 5% with 68% probability.

It is important to point out that, in cases in which very precise departure coefficients are needed, or to reduce the probability of failure during the iterative solution, one can utilize the GNN approximate values as initial populations for solving the NLTE problem. We have checked that, using the ALI method, this amounts to a reduction in the number of iterations needed for convergence of a factor between 2 and 4. Although relevant, the gain in computing time is not specially important because ALI methods become slower when getting closer to the solution.

3.3.2 Density conservation

The atomic level populations computed with a NLTE code fulfill, by construction, that their sum is equal to the total number density of the specific atomic species. For the specific case of our Ca II-Ca III atomic model:

$$\sum_i n_i = \sum_i b_i n_i^* = n_{\text{CaII}} + n_{\text{CaIII}}, \quad (3.9)$$

where we assume that the abundance of Ca I is negligible. Since the GNN is used to predict b_i , we need to check at which level the previous condition is fulfilled.

Fig. 3.4 shows the relative error in the normalization of the populations that we incur when using the GNN. Most of the predictions give abundances that are consistent throughout the whole atmosphere. We find deviations clearly below 2% with 68% probability, and below 5% with 98% probability.

FIGURE 3.3— Geometrical height distribution of the relative error between the correct departure coefficient and the one predicted with the GNN for all the Ca II and Ca III atomic energy levels. The median value is indicated with a solid blue line, while the shaded blue and orange regions indicate the 68% and 95% probability, respectively.

FIGURE 3.4— Height distribution of the relative error between the sum of the populations inferred with the computed departure coefficients and the true sum of populations for all the Ca II and Ca III atomic energy levels. The median value is indicated with a solid blue line, while the shaded blue and orange regions indicate the 68% and 95% probability, respectively.

3.3.3 Line profiles

Although the GNN produces a good approximation to the departure coefficients, the definitive check requires the synthesis of the line profile. According to Eqs. (3.6) and (3.7), errors in the predicted departure coefficients can be partially compensated. This is the case of the source function, where only the ratio between departure coefficients appear, while a good prediction of the departure coefficient for the lower level is fundamental for a good estimation of the opacity. In other words, one can still produce a good approximate line profile even if the approximate departure coefficients are not in excellent agreement with the correct one. To carry out this validation, we synthesized the line profiles for the Ca II K (in PRD) and 8542 Å (in CRD) lines at four representative locations in the 3D snapshot. We show the results in Fig. 3.5. The upper row displays the calculated departure coefficients (dotted) for all levels of the Ca II model, together with the neural prediction. The precise pixel in the simulation can be seen in the inset. Given the remarkable similarities on the departure coefficients, the level populations obtained from these approximate departure coefficients produce synthetic spectral lines at $\mu = 1$ (with μ the cosine of the

heliocentric angle) in NLTE that almost overlap with the full calculation (see Fig. 3.5). Note that the lines are asymmetric due to the presence of strong velocity gradients with height in the selected pixels. For comparison, we show in green the line obtained in LTE, which is trivially computed by setting $b_i = 1$.

FIGURE 3.5— Upper panels: original (dotted) and approximated (solid) stratification of the departure coefficients with τ_{500} for all relevant levels of the Ca II model atom on a few selected pixels from the Bifrost simulation snapshot shown in the right panel (we display the temperature map at $\tau_{500} = 1$). Middle panels: synthetic spectral line of the widely used Ca II line at 8542 Å using the original departure coefficients (blue) and the approximate ones (orange). For comparison, we also show the profile in LTE conditions in green. Lower panels: synthetic spectral line of the Ca II K line at 3968 Å computed in PRD.

With our GNN, the prediction of the departure coefficients takes around 25 ms in an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080Ti, when done in serial. This includes all the input/output operations required to load the input on the GPU memory and unload the results to the CPU memory. Exploiting the parallelization properties of GPUs, a batch of roughly 50 such models can be fit into typical GPU memory at once, producing similar computing times. On the other hand,

FIGURE 3.6— Generalization checks of a FAL-C model atmosphere to which a strong local increase in the temperature is added at different heights. The upper row shows the temperature stratification. The middle row shows the original (dotted) and approximated (solid) departure coefficients. The lower row shows the synthetic lines using the correct departure coefficients (blue) and the approximated ones (orange), together with the profile in LTE (green).

the computation of the departure coefficients with Lightweaver can take about 20 s in an Intel Xeon-6130 CPU @ 2.10 GHz. As a consequence, our approach produces a speedup factor of 10^3 with a negligible impact on precision. Arguably, larger speedups can be obtained with smarter graph constructions that require less message passing steps.

As an additional test, we carry out the experiment of computing the emergent line profile in the 8542 Å line when a strong localized heating occurs at different positions on the atmosphere. These models were not favored by the procedure followed for the generation of the training set, so they are a good generalization test. Additionally, they represent situations that could happen in the solar atmosphere. The results are summarized in Fig. 3.6. As shown in the upper panel of the figure, the proposed bump has Gaussian shape with an amplitude of 3000 K and a full width at half maximum of 0.7 in $\log \tau_{500}$ units. It is added to the temperature stratification of the FAL-C model. The central location of the heating is marked by the dashed grey line. The central row shows the correct (dotted) and approximate (solid) departure coefficients, with the same color code as that used in Fig. 3.5. Finally, the lower panel displays the emergent intensity profiles at $\mu = 1$. The line profiles are very similar to the correct ones, even though some differences exist in the central core. The differences are larger when the perturbations occur on the line formation region. These differences should then be taken as representative of the uncertainty in the line profile introduced by the GNN.

3.4 Inversions

The main goal of this work is to improve the current inversion methods by speeding up the process. As discussed in the introduction to this chapter, the GNN serves as the perfect machinery to carry out very fast NLTE inversions. To this end, we implemented it into the `Haze12` inversion code (Asensio Ramos et al. [2008]) for the inversion of observations of the Ca II 8542 Å line. `Haze12` utilizes the SIR machinery for the synthesis of lines in LTE. In order to synthesize the line in NLTE, the opacity and source function computed with SIR are modified according to Eqs. (3.7) and (3.8) in the CRD approximation, with the departure coefficients computed with the GN. Note that using the CRD approximation for the synthesis of the Ca II 8542 Å line is a good approximation because the GNN returns the departure coefficients with the Ca II H & K lines computed in PRD. The results of the `Haze12` inversion code, which includes the GNN, are shown in the following sections.

3.4.1 Response functions

As already mentioned in section 2.4, response functions are the derivative of the emergent line profile with respect to the physical conditions in the atmosphere. Having an accurate Jacobian turns out to be crucial for the development of a fast inversion code. We demonstrate with Fig. 3.7 that the GNN approximation gives good approximations to the response functions.

FIGURE 3.7— Response functions, in units of 10^{-12} , at four different optical depth heights for the FAL-C model atmosphere. The response functions are computed numerically using the full NLTE calculation (blue), the approximate GNN solution (orange), in LTE (green), and in the fixed departure coefficient case (red).

The response functions are computed in the FAL-C model on 6 nodes equispaced in $\log \tau_{500}$. The temperature of each node is perturbed by a small amount (± 25 K), and centered finite differences are used to compute the response functions. Four cases are considered in Fig. 3.7. The first one (blue) is the exact NLTE response function computed with Lightweaver. The second one (orange) uses the GNN to compute the departure coefficients. The third case (green) assumes that all departure coefficients are unity (LTE). The fourth case (red) assumes that the departure coefficients are not affected by the perturbation and are given by those of the unperturbed atmosphere. This is also known as the fixed departure coefficients (FDC) case (Socas-Navarro et al. [1998]). The FDC approximation clearly overestimates the response of the line to the temperature at the higher layers, as shown by Milić and van Noort [2017]. The response function is very similar to the exact one at lower layers for all approximations.

Our results clearly demonstrate that adding the dependence of the GNN on the physical conditions during the computation of the numerical derivatives leads to a very good approximation of the response functions. This anticipates the very good convergence results that we show in section 3.4.2.

3.4.2 Inversion results

Since `Haze12` computes response functions using finite differences, and the GNN is differentiable by construction, the influence of the departure coefficients are seamlessly included. This means that one is effectively working in the non-fixed departure coefficient case. Although not strictly necessary, we checked that departure coefficients do not need to be recomputed at every iteration. We empirically found good results by recomputing them only when the maximum change in the temperature during the inversion procedure is larger than 50 – 100 K.

Since inversion codes are routinely run in parallel supercomputers, the GNN cannot be run in a dedicated GPU, in general. Therefore, we need to resort to the less efficient CPU computation, which is roughly 10 times slower than a dedicated GPU. Even in this case, there is a significant computing time advantage of the NLTE option of `Haze12` with respect to any other NLTE inversion code. We assume ~ 250 ms and ~ 20 s for the computation of the departure coefficients using a GNN or the ALI iterative scheme, respectively. Consequently, our method is approximately a factor $f = (t + 20)/(t + 0.2)$ faster, where t is the time required for common tasks like computing hydrostatic equilibrium or solving the radiative transfer equation. Typical values are found to be $t < 0.1$ s, so that $f > 67$. In other words, one can carry out NLTE inversions only slightly slower than LTE inversions.

The data that we invert consist of a scan from a time sequence of full-Stokes measurements of a penumbral region taken at high spatial resolution with CRISP in the Ca II 8542 Å line. The data were obtained on 27 July 2020, between 08:35:09 and 08:52:48 UT. At the date, the hosting sunspot was located at a heliocentric distance of 25.8 degrees. During the observation, the Ca II 8542 Å line was sampled at 15 wavelength positions in the range $[-1.755, 1.755]$ Å, with steps of 65 mÅ close to the line center, and wider in the wings. Each scan was completed every 21 s. We acquired 12 accumulations per wavelength step and modulation state. The FOV of the observations is of about $55'' \times 55''$, and the pixel size is $0''.057$, which gives a total of 965×965 pixels. Due to the computational limitations of standard NLTE inversions, we only analyze a small subfield of 147×107 pixels, equivalent to $8.3'' \times 6.1''$. We carried out the data reduction using the SSTRED pipeline (de la Cruz Rodríguez et al. [2015], Löfdahl et al. [2021]), and images were restored using the Multi-Object Multi-Frame Blind Deconvolution technique (MOMFBD; Löfdahl [2002]; van Noort et al. [2005]). The inversions are carried out both with STiC and `Haze12`, taking into account the transmission profile of the CRISP instrument.

Given the differences between `Haze12` and STiC in terms of all the micro-

physics and the inversion procedure, we do not expect both inversions to give exactly the same results. Since our interest here is to investigate how the GNN works when applied to NLTE inversions, we put the emphasis on Stokes I and the temperature. The STiC inversions are done in three cycles. The first two cycles consider one every 10th pixel. We characterize the configuration of each cycle with the vector $(n_T, n_v, n_{v\text{mic}}, n_B)$, which gives the number of nodes in temperature, line-of-sight velocity, microturbulent velocity, and magnetic field components. The configuration for the first two cycles is $(7, 2, 1, 2)$ and $(7, 3, 3, 3)$. After the second cycle, we interpolate the results for all pixels and carry out a final cycle with $(7, 3, 3, 3)$. In *Haze12* we simply invert every pixel from scratch using two cycles with $(3, 1, 1, 0)$ and $(5, 2, 2, 1)$ using FAL-C as a reference model. The average inversion time per pixel with *Haze12* in an AMD Epyc 7452 CPU is 9.8 s.

FIGURE 3.8— Temperature stratification at different optical depth surfaces obtained with STiC (upper panels) and *Haze12* (lower panels). The letters refer to the position of the profiles displayed in Fig. 3.10.

The temperature maps at four different optical depth surfaces are shown in Fig. 3.8. The spatial appearance is remarkably similar between both inversion codes, with clear chromospheric structures appearing for layers above $\log \tau_{500} \leq -2$. The photospheric temperatures ($\log \tau_{500} \geq -2.5$) are essentially indistinguishable, not only in their aspect but also in the amplitude of the temperature. The results in higher layers ($\log \tau_{500} = -4.5$) are slightly different. The information encoded in the profiles for such heights is reduced and the results depend on the specific assumptions of the model and the details of the

inversion. This is not surprising since the CRISP data is undersampled, which surely produces a loss of sensitivity around the central core, which is sampling heights in the range $\log \tau_{500} = [-5, -4]$. For heights above these, one should not put any emphasis on existing differences among codes because the lines do not have any sensitivity (Quintero Noda et al. [2016]). Adding more lines that help sample these regions is the only way to produce a more constrained solution (da Silva Santos et al. [2018]).

For a more in-depth analysis of the difference between the results of the two inversion codes, we show in Fig. 3.9 the depth stratifications of the temperature, microturbulent velocity, and line-of-sight velocity for the four pixels marked in Fig. 3.8. `Haze12` is based on the strategy proposed by Ruiz Cobo and del Toro Iniesta [1992] of using a reference model as baseline. This model is iteratively modified at the nodes, and the node values are perturbations to the baseline model. It is obvious that the results of `Haze12` still display some memory from the FAL-C model used as reference. Meanwhile, `STiC` directly inverts the value of the physical properties at the nodes. The similarities between both results are obvious in the regions where there is sensitivity. The results are not expected to be exactly the same due to the differences between the two synthesis codes, the different parameterization of the solution, and how the iterative inversion proceeds. In the regions without sensitivity, both results might diverge, but this has negligible impact on the emergent profile. As discussed above, one should not focus on the differences in these regions of negligible sensitivity for the Ca II 8542 Å line.

Despite these differences in the stratification of the physical properties, the Stokes I profiles are correctly reproduced (given the noise) with the two codes. Figure 3.10 displays the Stokes I profiles for the four selected points. The green dots show the observed profile, with the orange and blue curves displaying the `Haze12` and `STiC` synthetic profiles in the inferred model, respectively. Both fits are of similar quality.

3.5 Remarks of the inversions with GNN

In this chapter, we have shown that NLTE problems (of the first kind) can be solved very fast using a graph network for predicting the value of the departure coefficients from the physical conditions. The forward evaluation of the GNN is orders of magnitude faster than the solution of the NLTE problem. This greatly accelerates the synthesis, opening up the possibility of quickly calculating synthetic profiles of strong lines with NLTE effects. In cases in which the approximate departure coefficients are not precise enough, one can use them as initialization for the full NLTE problem. This leads to a significant reduc-

FIGURE 3.9— Depth stratification of the temperature (upper panel), microturbulent velocity (middle panel), and line-of-sight velocity (lower panel) for the pixels shown in Fig. 3.8 inferred with STiC (blue) and Haze12 (orange).

tion on the computing time because fewer ALI iterations (between one-half and one-fourth) are needed.

Arguably the most straightforward application of our GNN is to accelerate NLTE inversion codes. As a proof of concept, we have implemented the neural approach in the Haze12 inversion code, so that it can use the LTE machinery of SIR to carry out NLTE inversions of Ca II lines. We find that the computing time is reduced by a significant factor when compared with classical approaches to NLTE inversions. Given all the uncertainties of a NLTE inversion procedure (observational noise, lack of flexibility of the model, ambiguities, uncertainties in the atomic data, etc.), our approximation turns out to be very competitive. The fact that we introduce a small error on the estimation of the departure coefficients is only an additional contribution to this inherent uncertainty.

We demonstrated the fast inversions with data from the CRISP instrument showing a good comparison with the results obtained with STiC. We point

FIGURE 3.10— Observed Stokes I profiles (green dots), together with the fits produced by STiC and Haze12. These profiles correspond to the pixel locations found in Fig. 3.8.

out that the implementation in `Haze12` can only be used for lines for which the CRD approximation is valid because it uses the SIR code internally. This is a suitable approximation for the Ca II infrared triplet lines. If lines need to be computed taking into account PRD effects, one needs to use codes like RH or HanleRT-TIC to solve the RTE. An acceleration of the inversion is still possible because the departure coefficients can be computed with the GNN and no MALI iteration is needed at all.

Although we have particularized all calculations to the prediction of the departure coefficients in 1D plane-parallel cases, graph networks are general. They can be seamlessly applied to higher dimensions and to arbitrary topologies and for the prediction of other quantities. An obvious extension of this work is to compute departure coefficients or mean intensities in 3D snapshots, taking into account horizontal radiative transfer effects, that have been proven to be significant in some scenarios (see Štěpán and Trujillo Bueno [2013], Jaime Bestard et al. [2021a]). This would require the solution of the 3D NLTE problem, something that can be done with codes like MULTI3D (Leenaarts and Carlsson [2009]) or PORTA (Štěpán and Trujillo Bueno [2013]). The main difficulty resides on the computational effort to find a sufficiently large training set, in combination with the memory requirements of a fully connected 3D graph. These limitations, among others, will be overcome in chapter 5, where we propose a novel methodology for 3D inversions.

We focused in this chapter on the computation of the departure coefficients for the energy levels of the Ca II model atom. However, the method is general and can deal with any atomic system or even combinations of them. Training such a GNN could be of potential interest to deal with recent multi-instrument inversions that use lines from Ca II with CRISP and CHROMIS on the SST, Mg II and Si IV with the Interface Region Imaging Spectrograph ([IRIS; De Pontieu et al., 2014]) and the Atacama Large Millimeter Array (ALMA) continua to map the chromosphere and the transition region (Vissers et al. [2019], da Silva Santos et al. [2020]).

Despite the good results provided by the GNN, some caveats are in order. First, our results are based on a pre-computed training set. If any of the assumptions used during the computation of this set need to be changed, the trained GNN is of no utility and a new training needs to be carried out. Second, although we have checked that the GNN generalizes correctly to some unseen models, the training set is obviously missing models that describe energetic events, like those occurring in flares. We anticipate that model atmospheres computed with the RADYN code (Carlsson and Stein [1992, 1997], specialized in flares) can also be included in the training set to aid in the generalization

properties for this kind of energetic events. This would probably require the inclusion of other physical quantities as new parameters of the nodes. Additionally, the assumption of hydrostatic equilibrium can be lifted in these dynamic models. Likewise, the Bifrost 3D snapshot corresponds to a relatively quiet region, while active regions are not part of the training set. Whenever a suitable MHD simulation of an active region including realistic chromospheres and transition regions is available, one can also add them to the training set. Finally, we need to explore improvements to the architecture and on the selection of hyperparameters to produce a GNN with lower generalization error in upper atmospheric layers.

4

Differential illumination and radiative transfer effects in the He I 10830 Å line

*The best part of our knowledge is
that which teaches us where knowledge leaves off
and ignorance begins.*

Border Lines of Knowledge in Some Provinces of Medical Science
Oliver Wendell Holmes (November 6th, 1861)

Different spectral lines form, in general, in different parts of the atmosphere, and they are sensitive to the physical conditions in their region of formation. Moreover, different lines present different sensitivities to the various plasma properties (e.g., the magnetic field). Consequently, some lines are more suitable than others for the study of particular properties of specific layers or structures in the Sun. In this chapter we discuss some of the particularities of the He I triplet at 10830 Å. These lines do not form in the quiet atmosphere, but they are observed in active regions, off-limb spicules, and in filaments and prominences. In spicules, filaments, and prominences, they show clear signatures of scattering linear polarization. They are sensitive to the magnetic field via the Zeeman and Hanle effects (although they enter the saturation regime of the Hanle effect for magnetic fields of the order of 10 G). For these reasons, the He I 10830 Å triplet has been widely used to study the magnetic field in these structures (e.g., Centeno et al. [2008], Lagg et al. [2004], Sasso et al. [2007]). In these studies

the relevant structure is usually modeled as an optically thin constant property slab. The optically thin assumption is applied in the sense that the radiation transfer within the slab is neglected and the radiation field is fully determined by the illumination coming from the underlying disk, but the slab is still allowed to have as much optical thickness as necessary to fit the observations. Our main objective in this chapter is to question this assumption, showing how a not too big optical thickness ($\tau \sim 1$) can already challenge it. Of particular interest is showing how this assumption can potentially impact the inferred magnetic field.

4.1 Introduction to the He I 10830 line

The theory of atomic line polarization, summarized in section 2.2 (see the monograph by Landi Degl’Innocenti and Landolfi [2004]), is formulated under the assumption of CRD. In the CRD limit, there is a lack of correlation between the frequencies of the absorbed and emitted photons in scattering processes, and it is a suitable approximation for the vast majority of atomic lines in the solar spectrum.

The multi-term model atom, described in chapter 7 of Landi Degl’Innocenti and Landolfi [2004], is the most suitable to describe the He I 10830 triplet, as it accounts for J -state interference in the incomplete Paschen-Back regime, necessary for the accurate modeling of these lines (Socas-Navarro et al. [2004]). For the CRD theory in the multi-term atom to be strictly valid, the incident radiation field must be flat over a frequency interval that is much larger than the natural width of the atomic states and, to ensure physical consistency, across a frequency range including all the transitions of a given multiplet. Due to the small natural width of the 10830 triplet lines, the first condition is automatically satisfied if the spectrum is flat across the whole triplet.

For these conditions to be satisfied, the absorption and stimulated emission transfer and relaxation rates within a multiplet have to depend only on the frequency independent radiation field tensor (see Eq. 2.14). We note that the $\phi(\nu)$ absorption profile is representative of the absorption across the whole multiplet and it thus has the shape of the absorptivity (η_I), and not necessarily that of a Voigt profile. Strictly speaking, this approach is more accurate when all the multiplet components have comparable contributions to the absorptivity and are illuminated by similar enough radiation fields, which is not necessarily true for the He I 10830 triplet. If this is not the case, we potentially need a different approach to model the multiplet lines, allowing for different radiation fields for the different components of the multiplet.

FIGURE 4.1— Energy of the magnetic sublevels of the lower (left panel) and upper (right panel) terms of the 10830 Å multiplet as a function of the magnetic field strength. The natural widths of the upper-term levels is about 10^{-5} meV, which is well below the plotting resolution. The zero energy offsets in each panel correspond to the mean energies of the respective terms.

4.2 Changes to the multiterm atom

Following the reasoning in the previous section, to better model the He I 10830 triplet, we need to account for different radiation fields. In the case of the He I the triplet is distributed into two components, where the blue components consist in the transition between the triplet-S state with $J = 1$ and the upper triplet-P state with $J = 0$, and the red component consist in two blended transitions between the triplet-S and the lower triplet-P states with $J = 1, 2$. This can be particularly important when the optical thickness of the slab is not negligible, as the radiation field anisotropy within the slab can be significantly different between the two components and with respect to that of the incident radiation field. In order to account for different radiation fields in the components of the He I triplet in the multi-term atom model without relaxing the CRD approximation, we need to neglect quantum interference between the blue component's upper level and any of the red component's upper levels. In this way, the radiation field is required to be flat only over the respective triplet components.

Generally, the further in energy two levels are, the less significant the quantum interference between them is. The separation between the $J = 0$ state, the upper level of the blue component of the 10830 triplet, from the rest of the states is about 30 GHz (or 0.1 meV), that is, about four orders of magnitude larger than the natural width of the Zeeman states, which is about 1.6 MHz (or 10^{-5} meV). This energy separation remains very large for magnetic fields with strengths up to ~ 5 kG, when some of the Zeeman components of the upper levels of the red component crosses with the blue component's upper level (see

Fig. 4.1). Therefore, for the typical magnetic fields found in the solar atmosphere, we can safely neglect quantum interference between the upper levels of the blue and red components, and thus we can consider different radiation fields for each component while fulfilling the flat spectrum requirement.

Consequently, the only difference with respect to the standard multi-term SEE (see section 2.2) is that, instead of considering a single radiation field for the whole multiplet, we distinguish between the radiation field in the red and blue components, forcing the quantum interference between magnetic states pertaining to different components to vanish. Therefore, instead of a single \bar{J}_Q^K radiation tensor common to all the triplet components, we now have \bar{J}_Q^K (red) or \bar{J}_Q^K (blue), resulting from the same average as in Eq. (2.14), but integrating over $\phi(\nu)_{\text{red}}$ or $\phi(\nu)_{\text{blue}}$. These absorption profiles only account for the contributions to the red or the blue component, respectively. The RT coefficients in the RT equation have exactly the same formal expression as the corresponding coefficients of Landi Degl'Innocenti and Landolfi [2004]. These relatively minor changes in the SEE allow us to consider a much broader set of physical scenarios. We implemented these SEE in a 1D RT code, which solves the NLTE problem of the generation and transfer of polarized radiation.

4.3 Numerical experiments

In this section we show the result of some numerical experiments to illustrate how accounting for differential radiation between the red and blue components of the He I 10830 triplet can impact the emergent Stokes profiles. We also test how the self-consistent RT solution affects the emergent Stokes profiles, since these RT effects are what potentially produce different radiation fields for the two components.

We compare the results obtained with our code with those obtained under the flat-spectrum assumption and neglecting the impact of RT effects on the atomic density matrix. For this physical scenario, the RT equations have the solution (see, e.g. Asensio Ramos et al. [2008]),

$$\mathbf{I} = [\mathbf{1} + \psi_O \mathbf{K}']^{-1} [(e^{-\tau} \mathbf{1} - \psi_M \mathbf{K}') \mathbf{I}_{\text{inc}} + (\psi_M + \psi_O) \mathbf{S}], \quad (4.1)$$

where $\mathbf{1}$ is the unit matrix, $\mathbf{K}' = \mathbf{K}/\eta_I - \mathbf{1}$, with \mathbf{K} the propagation matrix and η_I the absorption coefficient for intensity, \mathbf{S} is the source function vector, and \mathbf{I}_{inc} is the Stokes vector of the incident radiation (at the lower boundary of the slab). The coefficients ψ_O and ψ_M only depend on the optical depth along the propagation direction at the given frequency, and their expression can be found in Kunasz and Auer [1988]. Due to its simplicity and straightforward

evaluation, Eq. (4.1) is commonly used in practical applications for the inversion of spectropolarimetric data of the He I 10830 triplet (Asensio Ramos et al. [2008]).

As noted above, Eq. (4.1) is applicable if both \mathbf{K}' and \mathbf{S} are constant along the propagation ray. This is a good approximation if the optical thickness is below unity. We note that while this approximation does include radiation transfer via Eq. (4.1), it is not self-consistent, as the radiation field is assumed fixed and constant throughout the whole extension of the slab. However, for larger optical thicknesses, this approximation becomes unsuitable because RT starts playing a significant role (Trujillo Bueno and Asensio Ramos [2007]). The problem then becomes non-local and non-linear, and the notably different opacities of the red and blue components also lead to the non-fulfillment of the spectral flatness approximation.

We have checked that, in the optically thin limit, our calculations agree with the result of Eq. ((4.1)) for magnetic fields with strengths ranging from zero to several thousands of gauss (see section 4.3.2).

4.3.1 Impact on the radiation field anisotropy

In this experiment, we consider a slab with constant properties located at 6 Mm above the solar surface, with its normal axis parallel to the solar radius. The optical thickness of the slab is $\tau = 2$ in the center of the red component of the He I 10830 triplet. We solve the self-consistent RT problem in this slab model.

In this first experiment, we assume that the slab is unmagnetized ($\mathbf{B} = 0$) and we analyze the wavelength variation of the J_0^0 and J_0^2 (mean intensity and anisotropy, respectively) components of the radiation field tensor at different optical depths from the top, $\tau = 0$, to the bottom, $\tau = 2$, boundaries of the slab (see Fig. 4.2). In Eq. (4.1), the radiation field tensor is constant throughout the slab and spectrally flat (red dashed line, hereafter, the non-RT model). However, the radiation field tensor components in the self-consistent solution (solid curves, hereafter RT model) show a strong dependence on height due to the combination of RT effects and the differential absorption and emission in the red and blue components of the multiplet.

At the top of the slab ($\tau = 0$, dark blue curve), the mean intensity spectrum (left panel of Fig. 4.2) resembles the typical He I 10830 absorption profiles. This can easily be understood primarily in terms of the absorption of the incident intensity in the slab's bottom boundary. At the bottom of the slab ($\tau = 2$, yellow curve), however, the mean intensity shows an excess with respect to the mean intensity of the incident continuum radiation. This is due to the radiation that is emitted from within the slab and traveling "downward".

FIGURE 4.2— Mean intensity (J_0^0 ; left panel) and anisotropy (J_0^2 ; right panel) normalized to the incident continuum mean intensity ($J_0^0_c$) at different optical depths, τ , measured from the top boundary at the He I 10830 multiplet red component's center. Color coded are different optical depth layers of the fully consistent NLTE solution. The red dashed line corresponds to the mean intensity and anisotropy of incident radiation field (\mathbf{I}_{inc} in Eq. 4.1).

Regarding the radiation field anisotropy (right panel of 4.2), we see a reduction with respect to the incident anisotropy, a reduction which is non-monotonic with the optical depth. This reduction is mainly a consequence of the horizontal RT within the slab: for inclined lines of sight, there is a larger amount of emitting material, which increases the negative contribution of the radiation coming from directions forming an angle with the slab's axis that is larger than the van Vleck angle (see, e.g., Trujillo Bueno [2001]). For this reason, the largest differences between the non-RT and RT model's anisotropies are found at optical depths around $\tau = 1$, where the radiation is more likely to start escaping the slab along the vertical direction, while the more inclined rays are still optically thick.

From this experiment, it is clear that RT and the relaxation of the flat spectrum approximation can have a considerable impact on the radiation field tensors that (as we show in subsequent experiments) can significantly impact the emergent Stokes parameters.

4.3.2 Impact on the emergent Stokes profiles

Even with a relatively small optical thickness of $\tau = 2$, NLTE RT effects significantly modify the radiation field anisotropy within the slab. Since this quantity is crucial for the emitted linear scattering polarization, we can expect RT effects to have a significant impact on the emergent Stokes profiles as well.

We consider the same physical scenario as in Sect. 4.3.1, but with a uniform

and horizontal (perpendicular to the slab’s axis) magnetic field of $B = 10$ G. After solving the self-consistent NLTE problem, we calculate the emergent Stokes profiles for a line of sight parallel to the slab’s axis. We note that if the slab and the incident illumination at the bottom boundary are axially symmetric, as it would be the case if it was not for the chosen magnetic field, there would be no polarization when observing along the slab’s axis due to the symmetry. Thus, the magnetic field is necessary to generate scattering linear polarization via the Hanle effect in the chosen model and line of sight. This would correspond, for example, to the observation of a filament close to the disk-center. By choosing the reference direction for the linear polarization parallel to the magnetic field vector, the only non-zero Stokes parameters are I and Q .

Figure 4.3 shows the emergent Stokes profiles for three cases: i) the non-RT model (orange solid curve), ii) the RT model with the flat spectrum across the whole multiplet approximation (dashed blue curve, hereafter RT-flat model), and iii) the RT model (solid blue curve).

FIGURE 4.3— Intensity I (left panel) and Q (right panel) line profiles normalized to the continuum intensity for both the constant-property slab model solution (orange) and fully consistent NLTE solution (blue) for disk-center observation of the $\tau = 2$ slab with horizontal magnetic field with $B = 10$ G. The positive Q direction is parallel to the projection of the magnetic field vector onto the plane of the sky.

Regarding the intensity (left panel of 4.3), the impact of the approximations is relatively minor. Assuming (or not) a flat spectrum across the whole multiplet does not have a significant impact if one solves the self-consistent problem, and fully neglecting RT effects only has some impact on the depth of the red component. This difference could lead to a slight error on the determination of the optical thicknesses or the Doppler width (equivalently, the temperature) of the slab, but we do not expect such a difference to be significant.

One interesting aspect to note is what happens to the polarization (right panel of 4.3). The flat spectrum approximation in the self-consistent (RT-flat model) solution results in a significant increase of the emergent linear polarization, changing the ratio between the polarization signals of the blue and red components. Moreover, if RT is also neglected (non-RT model), the calculated emergent linear polarization is even larger, resulting in an increase by more than a factor of three with respect to the RT model.

Consequently, both RT effects and the flat-spectrum approximation have a significant impact on the linear polarization profiles. This difference in the signal is directly related to the changes in the frequency-independent anisotropy, as defined in Eq. (2.14), with the suitable absorption profiles. In particular, the anisotropy in the red component, which determines the alignment of the red component's upper levels, is smaller in the RT model than in the non-RT model in the whole slab; it is also smaller than the anisotropy of the RT-flat model in the upper part of the slab ($\tau \leq 1$) where most of the photons emerge from. Curiously, the anisotropy of the blue component is significantly larger than that of the RT-flat model and of the red component in the RT model (although it is still smaller than the anisotropy in the non-RT model). However, the blue component's upper level is non-polarizable ($J = 0$) and thus the polarization of this line is fully due to dichroism; namely, it is due to the atomic alignment of the lower level (Trujillo Bueno et al. [2002]). It turns out that the impact of the red component on the lower level alignment is characterized as being smaller/diminished when we relax the flat spectrum approximation and so, the emergent linear polarization in the RT model is consistently smaller across the whole multiplet.

We can further study the impact of these approximations by comparing the fractional linear polarization signal at the peaks of the blue and red components for different magnetic field strengths and for several optical thicknesses (see Fig. 4.4). For the chosen model (disk-center line of sight, axially symmetric slab model), the horizontal magnetic field breaks the axial symmetry and induces linear polarization. Up to a few gauss, in the Hanle regime, the polarization increases with the magnetic field. For larger magnetic field strengths, the Hanle effect is in saturation and the linear polarization is insensitive to changes in the magnetic field strength (plateau in the linear polarization in Fig. 4.4). For magnetic field strengths in the hundreds, the Zeeman effect starts affecting the linear polarization, as seen at the end of the plateau toward the largest field strengths in Fig. 4.4. For small optical thicknesses (e.g., $\tau = 0.01$, the optically thin limit; see top-left panel of Fig. 4.4), the three approaches produce (as expected) the same polarization signal for every magnetic field. However, for

increasingly larger optical thicknesses, RT effects induce a significant reduction of the anisotropy and thus of the polarization signal, which is more significant the larger is the optical thickness. This behavior will saturate when the optical thickness is large enough as to thermalize the bottom boundary of the slab. The relaxation of the flat-spectrum approximation also has an impact on the emergent linear polarization signals (compare the solid and dashed curves in Fig. 4.3), but the most significant reduction in the polarization emergent from the slab is due to RT effects (compare the dashed and dotted curves in the figure).

FIGURE 4.4— Fractional linear polarization, Q/I , as a function of magnetic field strength for different optical thicknesses specified at the top-left of each panel. The blue (red) curves correspond to the blue (red) component of the He I 10830 multiplet. The dotted curve shows the result with the non-RT model, the dashed curve shows the result with the RT-flat model, and the solid curve shows the result with the RT model. Note: the vertical-axis scale is different in each panel.

In summary, in this particular model, the NLTE solution leads to a significant decrease in the anisotropy within the slab and to a decrease in the He I 10830 polarization amplitude.

4.4 Consequences for the magnetic field inference

Given the change of the emergent Stokes profiles, the interpretation of the observations based on the optically thin slab model with the flat-spectrum approximation could lead to significant errors in the determination of the slab's physical properties, especially with respect to the magnetic field vector. This error can be critical depending on the particular physical scenario. For example, assuming an observation of a solar filament with a horizontal magnetic field in the Hanle saturation regime (e.g., 20 gauss), for which we are able to delimit its height¹, the non-RT model would overestimate the anisotropy and the inversion algorithm would need to pick a magnetic field strength in the Hanle regime (where the linear polarization is still sensitive to the magnetic field strength), in order to find a smaller polarization signal that fits the observation for the overestimated anisotropy. We would then infer magnetic field strengths in the fractions of gauss ($\mathcal{O}(10^{-1})$), instead of a magnetic field in the saturation regime ($\mathcal{O}(10^1-10^2)$). The opposite would happen in the prominence scenario, where a horizontal field depolarizes the zero-field scattering signal. In order to compensate for the excess in anisotropy from the non-RT assumption, the inferred magnetic field is increased, which could lead to the identification of field strengths of fractions of gauss ($\mathcal{O}(10^{-1})$) as magnetic fields in the saturation regime ($\mathcal{O}(10^1-10^2)$). We emphasize, however, that a non-RT model would also be unable to correctly fit the linear polarization profiles altogether. In the non-RT model, the ratio between the amplitudes of the red and blue components is fixed for each value of the signal of any of the two components. Because the ratio between these two signals with RT is different, there is no combination of parameters (in a constant property slab) for which the emergent Stokes parameters from Eq. (4.1) would adequately fit the RT profiles.

Although our conclusions are not model-dependent², their quantification indeed is. While the non-RT slab model shows these issues are due to the non-RT assumption, the RT slab model finds itself in the opposite extreme, that is, where the optical thickness tends to infinity in the horizontal direction.

¹If we are not able to determine the height of the filament, we would face a different problem with respect to an almost complete degeneration between height and magnetic field strength as inversion parameters.

²The very same argument can be made just by knowing that RT effects reduce the anisotropy, a fact that has been known for decades (Trujillo Bueno and Asensio Ramos [2007]).

We must thus emphasize that while our modeling exposes a potential problem in the inference of magnetic fields with the non-RT model, what we show in this work is the worst case scenario. First, the reduction of the anisotropy calculated in the slab is an upper limit. Secondly, the observation of circular polarization can alleviate the problem by providing a constraint in the magnetic field longitudinal component (we have intentionally chosen a physical scenario without circular polarization in this investigation), even though this cannot fully solve issues related to the direction of the magnetic field vector and it can even make it impossible to fit the four Stokes parameters simultaneously.

These findings are consistent with what was found in the observation and analysis of the He I 10830 triplet in prominences and filaments. In general terms, as explained above, it may explain why prominences seem to show magnetic fields in the saturation regime, while quiet Sun filaments seem to show magnetic fields in the fractions or units of gauss, namely, in the Hanle regime (see Trujillo Bueno and del Pino Alemán [2022], and references therein). Regarding the particular case of filaments, there are (as far as we know) only a few filament observations with the dichroic blue component signal, and the inversion is usually unable to achieve a completely satisfactory fit. Trujillo Bueno et al. [2002] showed a fit to a filament profile, demonstrating the dichroic origin of the blue component's linear polarization signal; however, their fit does not match the blue component's intensity (see their Fig. 4). Lagg et al. [2004] showed a fit to a profile in a flux emergence region, neglecting lower level polarization, that is unable to fit the blue component's linear polarization (see their Fig. 4 and 5). Later, Asensio Ramos et al. [2008] showed a fit to the same profiles including lower level polarization and, while it is improved, they were unable to simultaneously fit the linear polarization amplitude of both the blue and red components (see their Fig. 16, as well as Fig. 14 for an example with other filament observations). Díaz Baso et al. [2019a,b] found and studied this impossibility in the fitting, even though their observations show peculiar polarization signals with the same sign in both red and blue components, which require additional complexity in the physical model beyond RT.³ Other filament observations include those of Kuckein et al. [2012] and Xu et al. [2012], who found mostly Zeeman linear polarization profiles in filaments on top of active regions and thus could be fit (see Figs. 7-9 in Kuckein et al. [2012] and Fig. 4 in Xu et al. [2012]). Curiously, Kuckein et al. [2009] posit that a reduction factor of 0.2 was needed in the anisotropy in order to explain their filament

³We have not been able to find emergent Stokes profiles with the same sign signals with our code in a constant property slab, except for particular combinations of magnetic fields and velocities resulting in amplitudes much smaller than those observed.

observations, a similar reduction to the one we find in our model for the red component's anisotropy at $\tau = 1$ (~ 0.17 , see Fig. 4.2). All in all, observations of filaments in the He I 10830 triplet are relatively scarce, but they tend to show that the non-RT model may not be enough to find a satisfactory fit to the observed linear polarization profiles. Consequently, in order to correctly interpret observations in filaments with a relatively large optical thickness, we think that RT must be taken into account, the flat spectrum approximation must be relaxed, and that a model more complex than a constant property slab is necessary to explain observations, such as those of Díaz Baso et al. [2019a,b].

4.5 Summary and caveats

We have investigated the impact of RT effects on the polarization of the He I 10830 triplet. In particular, we have studied the effect that relaxing the flat spectrum approximation (requiring us to consider that both components are illuminated by identical radiation fields) has on the anisotropy and on the emergent linear scattering polarization. To this end, we have modified the SEE for the multi-term atom, neglecting quantum interference terms between the blue component's upper level and the two red component's upper levels. Moreover, instead of calculating a singular average radiation field for the whole multiplet (Eq. 2.14), we computed the equivalent quantity for each of the components, where the absorption profile is constructed by including only contributions to the absorptivity from magnetic line components pertaining to each of the blue or red components of the He I 10830 triplet. We implemented this modified set of equations into a 1D RT code and calculated the emergent Stokes profiles in a constant property slab model in order to compare our results with those obtained with the usual modeling assumptions of these lines, namely, no RT and flat-spectrum across the whole multiplet (non-RT model).

In the optical thin limit, our self-consistent calculations coincide with those of the non-RT model, as expected. As we increase the optical thickness of the slab, the results start to diverge and for an optical thickness that is not too large, we start to observe significant differences among the results. First, allowing for RT within the slab significantly affects the radiation field. The mean intensity in the top (bottom) region of the slab shows a significant defect (excess) in the lines due to the absorption (emission) by the rest of the slab below (above). The radiation field anisotropy is instead diminished with respect to the non-RT case due to the significant contribution of the radiation propagating along the more inclined directions, which are optically thicker due to the geometry, as anticipated by Trujillo Bueno and Asensio Ramos [2007].

More important, especially for the diagnostic of the magnetic field, are the

differences in the emergent Stokes profiles. For a slab of an optical thickness $\tau = 2$, we only find a small difference in the red component's intensity, which could slightly impact the determination of the optical thickness and temperature (via the Doppler width). However, the difference is remarkable for the linear scattering polarization, on the order of a factor three in the signal of both components. Due to the larger anisotropy in the non-RT model, which is diminished when horizontal RT within the slab is accounted for, the linear polarization is significantly overestimated. This can undoubtedly lead to an underestimation of the magnetic field or the filament height for this particular disk-center filament configuration. This would result in a difference that is potentially of a few orders of magnitude in the magnetic field strength in the worst-case scenarios. In fact, filament observations showing scattering polarization signals in the blue component, as far as we know, cannot be usually completely fit for both the blue and red components. Moreover, some observations show signals with the same sign in both the blue and red components something that we have not achieved in reproducing for a constant property slab even with RT. This could mean that the constant property slab model (both RT and non-RT) is too simplistic to model these observations.

The impact of the RT will be even more significant in full 3D geometry (e.g., Štěpán and Trujillo Bueno [2013]). First, a non-homogeneous volume of plasma with enough optical thickness will not only reduce the anisotropy of the incoming radiation from the underlying disk, but also contribute to the breaking of axial symmetry, an additional source of linear polarization, which can only be accounted for by the magnetic field in the commonly used slab model. Secondly, recent 3D NLTE RT calculations in an academic two-level atom model indicate that already for optical thicknesses as small as $\tau = 1$, RT plays an important role in spectral line formation (see Fig .9 of Štěpán et al. [2022]).

Last but not least, we note that another important multiplet of He I, namely, the D3 multiplet at 5876 Å, is most likely optically thin in all the structures of the outer solar atmosphere and, therefore, it is less prone to be impacted by the effects discussed in this paper. However, since the lower term of D3 is the upper term of the 10830 triplet, both multiplets are coupled. An investigation of the impact of the 10830 triplet transfer on the D3 lines remains one potential research topic for the near future.

The results presented in this chapter expose a potential problem of the simplified non-RT modeling of such complex structures. While its simplifications allow for the implementation of extremely fast inversion codes, we need to be careful when the plasma conditions do not allow for the simplifications to be

truly fulfilled. This emphasizes the relevance of developing novel diagnostic techniques that can account for important physical ingredients such as the full three-dimensional geometry and RT effects. For this reason, in the next chapter we will develop an inversion code based on the ideas presented in Štěpán et al. [2022], including both 3D and RT effects.

5

3D inversion code

*Far better an approximate answer to the right question,
which is often vague,
than an exact answer to the wrong question,
which can always be made precise.*
John Tukey (The future of data analysis.
Annals of Mathematical Statistics 33 - 1, 1962, page 13)

As we already mentioned in chapter 2, NLTE inversions of the solar atmosphere based on traditional grid discretization methods (where we discretize the atmosphere in 1D and assume that the atmosphere is horizontally homogeneous and semi-infinite) are computationally expensive. The main reason for this is that, even for such simplified geometries, computing the response of the emergent radiation to a change in each of the model parameters (which requires the self-consistent solution of the RT problem for each parameter) is a slow process.

Some efforts have been made to reduce the computational cost of the inversions, like introducing the concept of sparsity to use the spatial correlation present in the observations to accelerate and regularize the solution of adjacent pixels (Asensio Ramos and de la Cruz Rodríguez [2015]), the use of neural networks to accelerate part of the computations (Asensio Ramos and Díaz Baso [2019], Asensio Ramos and Socas-Navarro [2005], or Vicente Arévalo et al. [2022], see chapter 3), or physical simplifications of the problem, i.e., LTE, constant properties slab, or optically thin medium, among others. Among all the lines in the solar spectrum, those relevant to diagnose the chromosphere show NLTE effects and usually have optical thicknesses that exceed unity. In contrast

to the photospheric lines, in which we can safely use the LTE approximation. In this scenario, physical simplifications are not always possible nor desirable.

In the same way, in prominences and filaments RT effects (both in the plane of the sky and along the line of sight) are important if the plasma is not perfectly homogeneous and optically thin in every direction. This makes the optically thin constant properties slab assumption not always suitable, forcing us to solve the self-consistent RT problem in 3D.

The solution of the 3D inverse problem is thought to be almost impossible using traditional grid methods with the current computational resources, since the number of free parameters scales exponentially with the number of dimensions of the problem. Recently, new approaches have been proposed to solve the 3D inverse problem using a meshfree approach (Štěpán et al. [2022]), where the model parameters are decomposed in a set of basis functions and the atomic state variables (ρ_Q^K or \bar{J}_Q^K) and MHD variables ($T, \rho, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{v}, \dots$) are treated independently as an unconstrained minimization problem¹.

In this chapter, we introduce the meshfree approach to solve the 3D inverse problem (section 5.1). We present the implementation of the method in a 3D radiative transfer inversion code for the He I 10830 Å triplet (section 5.2) that we have dubbed POLARIS (POLARized Radiation Inversion Software). Then, we test the code in different forward modeling scenarios (section 5.3). Finally, we discuss these results in section 5.4.

5.1 Meshfree approach

To solve the 3D inverse problem without a grid discretization of the model atmosphere, we need an alternative way of representing the model parameters. In the meshfree approach, the model parameters are represented as a set of coefficients for certain basis functions that are defined in the whole domain of the model, and that can be evaluated at any position when necessary. If this was our only change to the inversion process, we would not achieve any significant improvement in computing time, since we still need to solve the forward problem with the lambda operator (or any equivalent accelerated methods). The real speed-up, and the main idea in the approach proposed by Štěpán et al. [2022], is to remove the need for a full self-consistent solution at every step of the inversion process by treating both the atomic and MHD variables as independent. This way, the inversion process becomes an unconstrained minimization problem where the model parameters are updated in each iteration using the gradient of

¹In contrast with the constrained minimization problem, in which every step of the inversion requires the atomic variables to be self-consistent with the set of MHD variables.

the cost function. The RT self-consistency appears as a regularization in this cost function instead, and it is evaluated in a random set of points (that we dub pilot points). The calculation of this regularization just requires calculating the atomic variables at the pilot points, for which we can use the long-characteristics (LC) method for a given angular quadrature. In this way, we are effectively removing the constraint imposed by the lambda operator (consistency at each step between the atomic and the MHD variables), and each step in the inversion procedure does not need to be self-consistent. If the unconstrained minimization process converges successfully, the solution is expected to be consistent (or almost consistent up to the uncertainties), as the self-consistency is part of the minimization process through the regularization.

5.1.1 Regularization in the meshfree approach

As already mentioned, the new approach allows for the solution of the 3D inverse problem without the direct constraint of self-consistency. As any meaningful solution of the inverse problem should be consistent with the physical properties of the plasma and the radiation field, we need to introduce a regularization term in the cost function. This term (as described in Štěpán et al. [2022]) is a penalty term that adds to the usual χ^2 term² in the cost function and is defined as,

$$\mathcal{L}_\Lambda(\theta) = \frac{1}{N_\Lambda N_\xi} \sum_{i=1}^{N_\Lambda} \sum_{k=1}^{N_\xi} |\xi(r_i; k) - \bar{\xi}(r_i, \theta; k)|^2, \quad (5.1)$$

where $\bar{\xi}(r, \theta; k)$ is the k -th atomic variable at point r_i of the model, obtained by solving the RTE with LC, and $\xi(r_i; k)$ is our guess for the same atomic variable. N_Λ is the number of pilot points where we check for self-consistency every iteration, N_ξ is the number of atomic variables, and θ are all the model parameters (both MHD and atomic variables). This term gets added to the χ^2 term in the cost function as:

$$\mathcal{L}(D; \theta) = \chi^2(D, \theta) + \lambda \mathcal{L}_\Lambda(\theta), \quad (5.2)$$

where D represents the observed data, and λ is a positive hyperparameter that weights the importance of the regularization term in the cost function. As the cost function should be minimized to obtain the solution, the \mathcal{L}_Λ term must be non-negative and differentiable. In this sense, it is clear that when $\mathcal{L}_\Lambda = 0$ the

²The L2-norm between the profiles of the observation and the inversion fit, commonly weighted with the observation uncertainties (see, e.g., del Toro Iniesta and Ruiz Cobo [2016]).

solution is self-consistent.³ Equivalently, when $\chi^2 = 1$ the solution is compatible with the observations within the noise. The value of the model hyperparameter λ can be chosen according to the specific problem to be solved and its value can be deduced from the required degree of consistency, i.e., the difference between $\xi(r_i; k)$ and $\bar{\xi}(r_i, \theta; k)$.

In addition to the self-consistency regularization term, our approach allows for the introduction of other regularization terms, \mathcal{L}_L , to force the solution to comply with other physical properties or constraints. For example, we can introduce a term penalizing the solutions not fulfilling the continuity equation $\nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v}) = 0$ in stationary models, or solutions in which the magnetic field is not solenoidal, i.e., not fulfilling $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0$. As with \mathcal{L}_Λ , the contributions to \mathcal{L}_L should be non-negative and differentiable. The term \mathcal{L}_L can be evaluated in a different (and generally bigger) set of points (that we dub regularization points), since these constraints are local and very cheap to evaluate from the computational point of view. The cost function is then,

$$\mathcal{L}(D; \theta) = \chi^2(D, \theta) + \lambda \mathcal{L}_\Lambda(\theta) + \gamma \mathcal{L}_L(\theta), \quad (5.3)$$

where γ is another positive constant modulating how much \mathcal{L}_L contributes to the cost function. Analogously to \mathcal{L}_Λ , \mathcal{L}_L tends to zero when the solution fulfills all the imposed physical constraints.

Is it worth mentioning that, even if the number of free parameters in the 3D inversion problem is much bigger than in the 1D case, the degeneracies of the solution could be smaller. This is because the 3D nature of the problem allows for much stronger constraints, both in the MHD and atomic variables, due to the spatial correlation of the observations, the spatial coupling by RT effects, and the additional regularization terms introduced in the cost function.

Another important aspect of the meshfree approach is that it allows, by fixing the MHD variables and removing the \mathcal{L}_L and χ^2 terms, for the solution of the 3D forward problem. In contrast to the inversion, such a forward solution will not generally be faster than the traditional grid-based methods, but it comes “for free” with the chosen approach.

5.1.2 Computational and memory requirements

In order to evaluate the advantages of our approach, it is of interest to make a comparison between the computational and memory requirements between the traditional discretized-grid and the meshfree approaches. To this end we first

³It would be strictly self-consistent in the pilot points, but RT spatially couples most of the domain, so the would be expected to be almost fully self-consistent, more the larger is the number of pilot points.

need to determine the number of parameters in the problem, which scales with the number of grid points in the discretized-grid and with the number of basis functions in the meshfree approach. Following Štěpán et al. [2022], for a square field of view with N^2 pixels,⁴ and for a given number of basis functions for MHD variables (M_ψ), of basis functions for atomic variables (M_ξ), of wavelength grid nodes (N_λ), of angular quadrature directions (N_Ω), of regularization points (N_L), and of pilot points (N_Λ), the minimization algorithm of the meshfree method scales as $O((M_\psi + M_\xi)(N_\lambda N^3 + N_\Lambda N_\Omega N_\lambda N + N_L))$,⁵ where each term in the summation corresponds to the scaling of the different terms in Eq. (5.3). By contrast, the discretized-grid method scales as $O(M_\psi N_\Omega N_\lambda N^3)$, so the ratio is,

$$\frac{O_{\text{meshfree}}}{O_{\text{grid}}} \sim \left(1 + \frac{M_\xi}{M_\psi}\right) \left(\frac{1}{N_\Omega} + \frac{N_\Lambda}{N^2} + \frac{N_L}{N_\Omega N_\lambda N^3}\right). \quad (5.4)$$

If M_ξ , M_ψ , and N_Λ are of the same order, the meshfree method has better scaling if $M_\xi < N^2$, and thus is superior for models and observations with high resolution and relatively limited spatial variability so M_ξ can be smaller. The discretized-grid method can still be superior for low-resolution models or with observations with a significant degree of spatial variability of physical parameters. In common applications, the meshfree approach is expected to be faster than the discretized-grid approach by several orders of magnitude.

5.1.3 Convexity of the problem and stochastic gradient descent

When applying the meshfree approach to the 3D inversion problem, we have found that the cost function is, in general, non-convex, what can be problematic in the optimization process. Such problems are related to the existence of local minima where the optimization algorithm can get stuck, preventing it from finding the overall optimal solution. To ameliorate this, we have introduced a stochastic distribution of the pilot points in the domain, reducing their number at the same time. This approach has two main effects in the optimization, first, the randomization introduces stochastic noise in the cost function, which can help avoiding local minima, and second, it speeds up the calculations, since reducing the number of pilot points reduces the number of calculations necessary to evaluate \mathcal{L}_Λ . Consequently, each iteration is very fast, but at the

⁴For simplicity we assume that the two sides of the field of view and the three sides of the grid for the discretized-grid method have the same size in pixels and grid nodes, N . This is a suitable approach because those sizes are expected to be of the same order for state-of-art observations.

⁵Note that we have used M_ψ and M_ξ for the total number of basis functions, and not for the number of basis functions for each variable as in Štěpán et al. [2022].

cost of increasing the necessary number of iterations. Given the characteristics of the gradient (i.e., noisy and stochastic with a large number of parameters) we chose the ADAM optimizer (Kingma and Ba [2017]) as the minimization algorithm. Finally, this stochastic approach also leads to a significant reduction in memory requirements, both because we do not need to allocate memory for too many pilot points (and their corresponding LCs) and because the memory efficiency of the ADAM optimizer.

5.2 He I 10830 Å module for POLARIS

In chapter 4 we show how a small modification in the SEE for the multi-term atom can allow for the modeling of the He I 10830 Å triplet partially relaxing the flat spectrum approximation within the CRD regime. Such modified SEE were implemented in a 1D forward synthesis code in Python. Python allows for fast development and flexibility in both testing and comparison with other traditional 1D algorithms, but it has a significant drawback in terms of computational efficiency making the code unsuitable for inversion purposes. With the objective of applying the 3D inversion code POLARIS to spectro-polarimetric data in the He I 10830 Å triplet, we have implemented the relevant equations in C++.

Our MHD variables are the temperature, the number density of He I atoms in the 10830 Å triplet levels, the damping parameter for the Voigt profile, the velocity vector, and the magnetic field vector. Note that we are directly inverting the relevant populations and, therefore, the only sensitivity to the temperature is via the Doppler width of the line, and therefore we do not expect an accurate inversion of the temperature structure. The formation of this triplet is rather complex, as it is believed that most of the population in the triplet system is due to the recombination that follows the ionization due to the ultraviolet radiation from the corona (Centeno et al. [2008]). Similarly to the constant property slab approach, in which the optical thickness is an inversion parameter, we bypass the issue by inverting the total population. It is thought that radiative and spontaneous processes dominate the formation of these lines, and thus the role of inelastic collisions is usually neglected in their modeling. As far as we know, the role of elastic collisions with neutral hydrogen has not been studied in detail, and they may possibly play a role in sufficiently dense active region filaments. However, it is believed that, in general, they are unlikely to significantly reduce the atomic polarization of the He I levels (Sahal-Brechot et al. [1977], Casini et al. [2009]). We thus do not include collisions in our SEE.

Our atomic variables are the components of the frequency integrated radiation field tensor, \bar{J}_Q^K , for the the red and blue components of the triplet (see

Vicente Arévalo et al. [2023] and chapter 4 for further details). Note that an analogous derivations could be done using the atomic density matrix components ρ_Q^K of the He I atom instead. Not all the components of the radiation field tensor are independent, and thus we use only those components with $Q \geq 0$, as $J_{-Q}^K = (-1)^Q (J_Q^K)^*$.

Considering that the components of the radiation field tensor are complex numbers, except when $Q = 0$, we end up with 18 atomic variables (9 for each triplet component). The atomic module needs to, given a position in the computational domain and the current guess value for the coefficients of the expansion in the chosen basis of the MHD and atomic variables, to compute the RT coefficients necessary to solve the RTE along long-characteristics. The RT coefficients depend on the density matrix elements, therefore the module must solve the SEE to obtain them from the current guess of the expansion coefficients of the radiation field tensors and the magnetic field vector. Finally, the module takes care of calculating the \mathcal{L}_Λ contribution to the cost function, that is, performing the angular and frequency integration of the Stokes parameters resulting from the solution of the RTE along long-characteristics (see Eq. 2.7) and applying Eq. (5.1).

5.3 Forward modeling tests

In order to validate the implementation of the He I module in POLARIS (the rest of the POLARIS code was tested with a much simpler academic atomic model) we carry out a series of forward modeling tests aimed at verifying the replication of several critical physical phenomena.

We compute a set of forward solutions for a 1 Mm^3 box with constant properties located 5 Mm above the solar surface. The lines of sight (LOS) and the physical properties of the plasma were different for each forward solution. We chose two LOS, one where the box is observed off-limb, with the center of the box in the plane of the sky (analogous to the prominence case), and another in which it is observed on the disk center (analogous to the filament case). For each LOS we carry out three experiments, i) $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{v} = 0$. ii) $\mathbf{B} \neq 0$ and $\mathbf{v} = 0$, and iii) $\mathbf{B} \neq 0$ and $\mathbf{v} \neq 0$. The values for the magnetic and velocity vectors for the six experiments are detailed in Tab. 5.1, and the geometry of the problem is shown in Fig. 5.1.

The rest of variables are common for all numerical experiments, with a temperature of 8700 K, a density of 100 cm^{-3} , and a damping parameter of $a = 10^{-5}$. This results in an optical thickness at the peak of the red component of about $\tau \sim 0.01$. The starting J_Q^K are $J_Q^K = 0$ except for $J_0^0 = 10^{-5}$ and $J_0^2 = 10^{-7}$. We have intentionally chosen experiments in the optically thin regime in

order to avoid radiative transfer effects for a straightforward comparison with the 1D results.

LOS	Off-limb			Disk-center		
Experiment	i	ii	iii	i	ii	iii
Case index	1	2	3	4	5	6
\mathbf{B} (G)	(0,0,0)	(0,100,0)	(-100,0,0)	(0,0,0)	(0,100,0)	(0,0,100)
\mathbf{v} (km·s ⁻¹)	(0,0,0)	(0,0,0)	(10,0,0)	(0,0,0)	(0,0,0)	(0,0,-10)

TABLE 5.1— LOS and magnetic and velocity field vectors for each numerical experiment described in the text and shown in Fig. 5.1.

FIGURE 5.1— Geometry (not to scale) of the numerical experiments described in the text and summarized in Table 5.1. The center of the Sun is at the origin of the coordinate system. The LOS are represented in dashed lines and are contained in the plane of the figure. The cubic box represents the volume of the model where the forward solution is computed. The circled numbers indicate the case index for the experiments listed in Table 5.1.

The emerging profiles for all experiments are shown in Figs. 5.2 and 5.3, respectively. Note that we have chosen the reference direction of the polarization in such a way that Stokes $U = 0$.

The results for the off-limb LOS are shown in Fig. 5.2. These experiments mimic a prominence observation. For experiment (i) we can see the typical signature of the 90° scattering in the linear polarization of the red component, and no circular polarization. In experiment (ii) the magnetic field is perpendicular to the LOS and to the quantization axis, depolarizing the linear scattering

FIGURE 5.2— Intensity I (top left panel), Stokes Q (top right panel), Stokes V (bottom left panel) normalized to the maximum intensity I_{\max} , and optical thickness (bottom right panel) resulting from experiments 1, 2, and 3 in Table 5.1 (off-limb LOS). The reference direction for the linear polarization is the parallel to the limb (y axis in Fig. 5.1).

polarization. In experiment (iii) the profiles are blueshifted (the box is moving toward the observer), the magnetic field (parallel to the LOS) produces circular polarization, and it has the maximum effectiveness in depolarizing the atom, resulting in almost no Stokes Q signal.

FIGURE 5.3— Same as Fig. 5.2, but for experiments 4, 5, and 6 in Table 5.1 (disk center LOS). The reference direction for the polarization is along the x axis in Fig. 5.1.

The results for the disk-center LOS are shown in Fig. 5.3. These experiments mimic a filament observation. In experiment (i) the problem is axially symmetric and thus there is no scattering polarization. In experiment (ii) the magnetic field is perpendicular to the LOS and the quantization axis, breaking the axial symmetry and producing linear polarization. In experiment (iii) the profiles are redshifted (the box is moving away from the observer), the magnetic field (parallel to the LOS) produces circular polarization, but due to the axial symmetry there is no Stokes Q signal.

It is worth noticing that in these tests we are looking for the overall behavior of the code and not the fine-tuning of the exact values.

5.4 Conclusions

In this chapter we have summarized the basic aspects of the POLARIS code, a numerical code for the 3D inversion of spectro-polarimetric data with radiation transfer based on a meshfree approach. In particular, we have described how POLARIS solves an unconstrained optimization problem, and it is its unconstrained nature what makes the inversion problem solvable with the computational resources available nowadays. We have also developed the atomic module for the modeling of the He I 10830 Å triplet, based on the approach described in chapter 4 to partially relax the flat spectrum approximation and account for differential illumination between the triplet components while still accounting for quantum interference between the two upper levels of the red component. We have carried out a series of simple but necessary tests to demonstrate the capability of the optimization procedure to find the physically consistent solution (or at least a solution very close to it) and reproduce the expected spectral features for Doppler shifts and the Hanle and Zeeman effects. We are thus ready to apply POLARIS to the inversion of spectro-polarimetric profiles, which is the topic of the next chapter.

6

3D inversion of a solar prominence

*An idea, like a machine,
must have power applied to it
before it can accomplish anything.*

B.C. Forbes

In this chapter, we apply POLARIS to spectro-polarimetric observations in the He I 10830 Å triplet of a solar prominence (Martínez González et al. [2015], Martínez González et al. [2016]). The prominence has two very bright feet that connect the much fainter spine at the top with the underlying chromosphere. This kind of prominences were first named "tornadoes" by Pettit [1932] since the feet appear as vertical funnel-like structures that seem to rotate, resembling the Earth tornadoes. However, the rotation is very likely just an optical illusion and the apparent rotation motions are due to waves, counterstreaming motions, or a combination of both (Luna et al. [2015], Panasenco et al. [2014]).

The original analysis of this spectro-polarimetric data was carried out with the HaZeL inversion code (Asensio Ramos et al. [2008]). The authors claimed mostly vertical magnetic fields of the order of ~ 20 G forming a helical structure by relying on a stability criterium. A-posteriori information was needed since the analysis resulted into two spectroscopically ambiguous solutions with very different geometries: vertical and horizontal fields, both being helical. In this analysis, every pixel was modeled as an independent optically thin slab of constant properties, i.e., each pixel was modeled as a slab of plasma floating in the vacuum above the solar disk. Despite the prominence being clearly non-homogeneous in the plane of the sky, it is considered homogeneous along the

line of sight. Even though the inferred optical thickness in the prominence is of about 2 on average, the radiation within the slab is not allowed to change due to radiation transfer effects. Moreover, even if there can be non-negligible optical thickness along the line of sight, the optical thickness between each pixel and the underlying solar disk is assumed to be identically zero, so every pixel (slab) receives the full, unperturbed, and axially symmetric solar disk radiation.

The POLARIS inversion code allows us to account for radiation transfer and differential illumination effects, that can have a critical impact on the resulting Stokes parameters and, consequently, on the inferred magnetic field (Vicente Arévalo et al. [2023] and chapter 4). Moreover, as POLARIS includes full 3D radiation transfer effects, it accounts for the attenuation and breaking of axial symmetry produced by the absorption of the disk radiation by the prominence material that is closer to the disk for any spatial point in the domain. Both the parameterization in coefficients of an expansion in basis functions and the 3D radiation transfer effects spatially couple (potentially) all points in the computation domain, what should lead to smoother and more spatially consistent solutions, as well as to a more constrained solution with no need to include information a posteriori.

In this chapter, we first describe the observations (sections 6.1–6.2) and the inversion setup (section 6.3). We then present the results of the POLARIS inversion, comparing them with the results of the first analysis of the data (section 6.4). Finally, we discuss the results of the inversion in section 6.5.

6.1 Observations

The observations were performed on April 24, 2011 (11:00-13:30 UT), using the Tenerife Infrared Polarimeter (TIP-II Collados and et al. [2007]) at the German Vacuum Tower Telescope (VTT) in the Observatorio del Teide, Tenerife, Spain. The observed region hosted a quiescent prominence located at $90^\circ\text{E } 42^\circ\text{S}$ in heliocentric coordinates. Four scans were performed in the 2.5 hours of observations, with steps of $0''.6$, integrating for 30 s (about 30 min per scan). The atmospheric conditions were excellent and the adaptive optics system allowed for a spatial resolution close to the diffraction limit of the telescope, about $0''.6$, coinciding with the chosen scan step. Standard reduction techniques were applied to the data, including dark and flat field corrections. The data was then binned in steps of two pixels along the slit direction, resulting in a polarization noise of about $7 \cdot 10^{-4}$ in terms of the maximum intensity and in a sample size of $0''.32$. Moreover, stray-light from the disk was reduced by fitting the observed intensity in each wavelength to its gradient and second derivative, and polarized interference fringes were also reduced by fitting sinusoidal functions

(more details in Martínez González et al. [2015]). As in the work of Martínez González et al. [2015], in this thesis we focus our analysis on the third of the scans, in which the “helical” features of the feet are more prominent.

We selected a wavelength range including only the He I 10830 Å triplet lines (see Fig. 6.1). For the original analysis with the HaZeL code the intensity values were not relevant, and the profiles were normalized to the maximum intensity counts. When solving the 3D problem consistently, however, we need to give actual intensity units to the observations. To this end we have used the intensity and limb darkening tabulations in Cox [2000] and fitted the transformation factor using 6 points inside the solar disk. We determined the continuum value in our observations from the red extreme of the spectral range (Fig. 6.1). In Fig. 6.2 we show the intensity map at the center of the red component of the He I 10830 Å triplet, already calibrated to the intensity units.

FIGURE 6.1— Sample intensity spectra from the observations. The red vertical line indicates the position of the center of the red component of the He I 10830 Å triplet. The orange line shows the continuum used for the calibration of the intensity units. The shaded area is excluded from the data in the inversion.

We choose the reference direction of the polarization parallel to the x -axis of the image (see Fig. 6.2). We have thus rotated the linear polarization signal from its original reference, parallel to the solar limb, to our reference. In Fig. 6.3 we show maps for the Stokes parameters at the center of the red component of the triplet.

FIGURE 6.2— Intensity map at the center of the red component of the He I 10830 Å triplet. The white and green curves show the positions of the limb and of an approximation of the upper limit for the location of spicular material, respectively. The red squares show the position used to fit the transformation factor from intensity counts to intensity units. The zero in the x and y axes is the disk center, with the positive values corresponding to the N–E direction.

6.2 Constant property slab analysis

In this section we summarize the analysis of these data carried out in Martínez González et al. [2015] and Martínez González et al. [2016]. On the one hand, there are some preliminary steps of the the preparation of the data for their inversions that provide useful information for setting up our own inversion. On the other hand, it facilitates the comparison with our results in section 6.4.

The position of the prominence with respect to the plane of the sky is critical for the inference of the magnetic field. This position, together with the position in the field of view, determines both the height and the scattering angle for the constant property slab, critical quantities for the linear scattering polarization. Martínez González et al. [2015] used images from the Atmospheric Imaging Assembly (AIA, Lemen et al. [2012]) at 171 Å to determine the position of the prominence feet on the solar disk. By tracking these positions over time, and backtracking them in time with the solar rotation, they were able to estimate

FIGURE 6.3— Intensity I (top left panel), Stokes Q (top right panel), Stokes U (bottom left panel), and Stokes V (bottom right panel) for the reconstructed observation at the center of the red component of the triplet. The points outside the region of interest (disk and regions where $I < 2.5 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ erg} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) are masked out.

the 3D position of the prominence in the observation. The resulting scattering angle was about 98° , that is, the prominence is slightly behind the plane of the sky. For us, this result is essential for positioning our computational domain relative to the solar surface and the observer.

By applying the HaZeL code pixel by pixel, Martínez González et al. [2015] inferred the magnetic field vector in the body of the prominence. Due to the 90° ambiguity of the Hanle effect in the saturation regime, they obtained two compatible solutions, one with mostly horizontal (with respect to the local vertical) and another with mostly vertical magnetic fields, both twisted. They chose the mostly vertical solution following the Kruskal-Shafranov criterion (Hood and Priest [1979]), as it is the more stable configuration and the one likely to last for the observed lifetime of the prominence. They thus posed that the magnetic field in the prominence is helical and mostly vertical, forming a

double helix structure.

Regarding the dynamics of the prominence, they determine that the velocity pattern was consistent with oscillatory motions due to MHD waves and, if there exist a rotation of the prominence feet, it must be intermittent, lasting no more than one hour. In this chapter we carry out the inversion of a single snapshot, and thus an analysis of the time series similar to that in Martínez González et al. [2016] is out of the scope of this investigation.

6.3 Inversion setup

In this section, we describe the main aspects of the inversion setup. We first describe the computational domain, i.e., the position, orientation, and size of the computation box (see section 6.3.1). We then define the inversion variables, their expansion in basis functions, their normalization value, and their initial values (see section 6.3.2).

6.3.1 Computational domain

The computational domain is the 3D volume where the variables of the inversion can take values and where the \mathcal{L}_Λ and \mathcal{L}_L contributions to the cost function can be evaluated. As mentioned in section 6.2, the prominence is slightly behind the plane of the sky. We calculated the location on the plane of the sky by fitting the limb in the observation with a circle, and adjusted the pixel size in the scan direction accordingly. The computational domain is then a box of $\sim 50 \text{ Mm}^3$, centered in the prominence, with its z axis parallel to the local vertical (at its center), and with its bottom (surface at minimum z) located about 0.1 Mm above the solar surface. In Fig. 6.4 we show this computational domain in the graphical user interface we have developed to facilitate its configuration and visualization.

In order to facilitate the convergence of the inversion problem, we have masked both the disk and the off-limb region where spicules are present. The sharp decrease in radiation at the limb puts a strain on the fitting of the variables in terms of basis functions, i.e., the basis functions and their coefficients would need to accommodate the limb in the whole FOV and, in general, we would need a significantly larger number of them. Likewise, the Stokes profiles in spicules are clearly different from those in the prominence, and the physical scenario is likely different (e.g., Tei et al. [2020]), and thus the requirements on the basis functions for the prominence and the spicules are different as well.

FIGURE 6.4— To the left, the computational domain (box within blue lines), and the field of view (square within green lines) for the inversion of the prominence data. The inset shows the projection of the domain onto the plane of the sky. To the right, parameters defining the position, size, and orientation of the computational domain, and the position and orientation of the observer. This figure has been extracted from the graphical user interface that we have developed to facilitate the configuration and visualization of the computational domain.

6.3.2 Variables and normalization

In the inversion of the prominence we have 9 MHD variables, the temperature, T , the He I triplet number density, \mathcal{N} , the damping parameter of the Voigt function, a , the three components of the velocity vector, \mathbf{v} , and the three components of the magnetic field vector, \mathbf{B} . As mentioned in chapter 5, we solve an unconstrained problem in which we do not solve the self-consistent problem at every step of the inversion, but we instead consider the relevant quantities (radiation field or density matrix) as inversion variables and the self-consistency is introduced as a regularization in the minimization problem. Our atomic variables are the independent components of the radiation field tensor for each

of the He I 10830 Å components, $\bar{J}_{Q_{\text{blue}}}^K$ and $\bar{J}_{Q_{\text{red}}}^K$. Each \bar{J}_Q^K has 9 independent components, and therefore we have 18 atomic variables. The number of variables is thus 27.

We fit the coefficients of the expansion of these variables in basis functions, that we chose to be Chebyshev polynomials. By projecting the intensity map at a given wavelength into a 2D basis of these polynomials, we found that we would need 16 of these functions in each direction in order to accurately reproduce the observed map. This is a significant number of coefficients (in 3D we would have $16^3 = 4096$, per variable). We instead start with a much smoother set of functions, with 5–7 coefficients. This not only reduces the computational cost, but the calculation is less prone to fall into local minima. The calculations with the reduced number of basis functions provide us with an average (smoothed) distribution of the MHD variables and allow for a more efficient exploration of the optimal parameters for the inversion (e.g., the coefficients for \mathcal{L}_Λ and \mathcal{L}_L in the cost function, see Eq. 5.3). Moreover, if a more refined inversion is required, we can increase the number of basis functions and use the smoother solution as the initialization of the inversion problem, what should in general result in a faster convergence of the inversion with larger number of basis functions than if it was started from a guess model further from the solution and from self-consistency.

For 5^3 , 6^3 , or 7^3 basis functions, we have 3375, 5832, and 9261 coefficients, respectively, which are the actual total number of free parameters. These numbers are also the optimal number of CPUs to run POLARIS with, as each CPU can take care of calculating the derivative of the cost function with respect to each of the free parameters (a larger number of CPUs would not result in a speed-up).

The \mathcal{L}_L contribution to the cost function includes the a priori knowledge about the inversion variables, which is introduced as a regularization in the minimization problem. For the inversion of the prominence we can add several constraints, i) the solenoidal condition of the magnetic field, $\nabla B = 0$, ii) limits on the expected temperatures, $T \in (2 \cdot 10^3, 5 \cdot 10^4)$ K, iii) positive number density, $\mathcal{N} > 0$, iv) positive mean intensity, $\bar{J}_0^0 > 0$, and v) the constraint $|\bar{J}_Q^K| < J_0^0$.

In order to account for the different orders of magnitude among the 27 variables, that can skew the derivative and prevent the solution of the inversion problem, all the variables are normalized. This normalization is such that the typical normalized value of each variable is of the order of unity. Due to the wide range of values possible for the density, this variable is defined in logarithmic scale. Moreover, the radiation field components $\bar{J}_Q^{K>0}$ are defined as a fraction

with respect to the mean intensity for each respective triplet component.

We initialize the inversion with an homogeneous plasma cube with $T = 5000$ K, $\mathcal{N} = 0.1 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $a = 0.1$, $\mathbf{v} = 0$, $\mathbf{B} = 0$, $\bar{J}_{0_{\text{blue}}}^0 = \bar{J}_{0_{\text{red}}}^0 = 10^{-5} \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, and $\bar{J}_{Q_{\text{blue}}}^{K>0} = \bar{J}_{Q_{\text{red}}}^{K>0} = 0$.

Finally, to compensate for the difference in order of magnitude between the different Stokes parameters in the calculation of the merit function χ^2 , we add the following weights in its calculation, $(w_I, w_Q, w_U, w_V) = (1, 100, 100, 150)$, based on their typical values in the observation.

6.4 Results

The inversion of the entire FOV, comprising 223×60 pixels, requires approximately $1.8 \cdot 10^5$ CPU hours to perform 10^4 iterations with the current version of our helium atomic module in POLARIS, assuming the use of 5^3 basis functions. This corresponds to an average of 13.5 CPU hours per pixel. The 3D inversion of spectro-polarimetric observations with self-consistent radiation transfer is clearly intensive from the computational point of view. While we have non-priority access to the LaPalma supercomputer, located at the Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias and part of the Spanish Supercomputer Network, the amount of available CPUs and the typical degree of oversubscription (which entails long waiting queues) make it not very well suited for the needs of this project. For this reason, we applied (successfully) for 2.5 million CPU hours in the MareNostrum Supercomputer in Barcelona for the second period of 2024 (from July to October). Unfortunately, due to time constraints, the thesis manuscript can only include the first results of the inversion, with the smoother solutions with 5^3 basis functions. Nevertheless, we consider that the results of these inversions are already interesting and worthwhile to present, as well as a significant step forward in regard to our prominence diagnostic capabilities.

6.4.1 Convergence and Stokes parameters

In Fig. 6.5 we show the cost function and its contributions in the inversion with 5^3 basis functions. Note its monotonically decreasing behavior, indicative of the inferred model approaching a solution both fitting the profiles (χ^2) and fulfilling the radiation transfer self-consistency (\mathcal{L}_Λ).

FIGURE 6.5— Convergence of the merit function for the Stokes profiles χ^2 (black curve), self-consistency contribution to the cost function \mathcal{L}_Λ (green curve), and total cost function \mathcal{L} (red curve), for an inversion of the prominence data with 5^3 basis functions.

We suggest that further tests should be performed with a different number of basis functions and pilot points to see how the resolution of the inversion is affected. It is possible that with 5 basis functions per dimension the inversion was not able to reproduce the fine details of the observations. Following from this solution, higher resolution can be achieved at the cost of more computing time.

We show the Stokes parameters maps at the central wavelength of the red component of the triplet (for I , Q , and U) and for the wavelength showing the maximum circular polarization signal (for V) from the observation and from the Stokes profiles emerging from the inferred model in Fig. 6.6. Note that the white shaded regions in the intensity panels show regions of the field of view that are masked in the inversion, and those regions are thus not being included in the fitting procedure (in practice, masked points cannot contribute to χ^2). As expected, the relatively small number of basis functions (5 per dimension) result in maps that are smoother than the observation. Nevertheless, the inferred model can reproduce the main features of the observation (as much as the resolution of the model allows for), including the denser feet, the fainter region connecting the feet, and the structure and signs of the polarization in most of

FIGURE 6.6— Intensity I (top row), Stokes Q (second row), Stokes U (third row) at the central wavelength of the red component of the triplet, and Stokes V (bottom row) at the wavelength where it is maximum in absolute value for each pixel, for the observations (left column) and the profiles emerging from the inferred model (right column). The green line indicates the maximum distance from the limb were Stokes profiles typical of spicular material are observed. The shaded grey area shows the masked region, not included in the calculation of χ^2 . And the points where $I < 2.5 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{erg} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ are zeroed in Q, U, V , to remove low S/N pixels. The colored circles indicate the location of the pixels whose profiles are shown in Fig. 6.7.

the prominence.

In order to evaluate the goodness of the actual fits to the profile, in Fig. 6.7 we show the Stokes profiles for five representative pixels taken at different positions in the prominence, covering different combinations of polarization signs and density regimes. If we take into account that, i) the resolution of the inferred model is quite limited, ii) the inversion still has room for improvement, and iii) the unconstrained optimization nature of the procedure, the fits are remarkably good. The worse fits in the selected pixels happen for the circular polarization V (see P2 and P3 in the figure), what can be due to the number of basis functions not being enough to reproduce the fine structure of the magnetic field vector up to below 1% in the emerging polarization. The fit of the

intensity in P5 is not excellent, however, we need to consider that this pixel corresponds to a location at the fainter cloud connecting the prominence feet. A closer look to the intensity map reveals a more “clumpy-like” structure in that fainter region. Therefore, the lower quality of the fit for P5 is very likely due to the limited resolution of the model with 5^3 basis functions.

FIGURE 6.7— Intensity I (top row), Stokes Q (second row), Stokes U (third row), and Stokes V (bottom row) for the observations (circles) and the inversion fit (solid curves). From left to right, pixels selected at different positions in the FOV, indicated with circles in Fig. 6.6 with the same color.

6.4.2 Inferred model

The product of our inversion are the coefficients for the expansion in basis functions for the 27 variables. The 18 atomic variables, the multipolar components of the radiation field tensors for the two components of the triplet, are determined by the self-consistency of the model, introduced via regularization. The variables of interest are the 9 MHD variables.

We have included \mathcal{N} and a as free parameters (see section 5.2), thus neglecting the relation between number densities and temperature and gas pressure via an equation of state. Consequently, in our inversion the profiles are weakly

FIGURE 6.8— Density isosurfaces (bottom colorbar) of the reconstructed density distribution. Magnetic field lines (top colorbar) are shown at the base (top left) of the prominence. The mask used in the inversion (see Fig. 6.6) is considered when rendering the volumetric distribution. The reference frame is indicated at the bottom left and the orientation is as seen by the observer along the positive Z axis.

sensitive to the temperature, via the Doppler width of the lines, and thus we cannot retrieve an accurate mapping. Nevertheless, the obtained temperature is $T \in (5, 15\,000)$ kK in the whole domain, relatively far from the limits imposed via regularization (see section 6.3.2).

By contrast, the distribution of \mathcal{N} determines the spatial distribution of the prominence mass (actually the amount of population in the He I triplet), which is critical for the emerging intensity. Volumetric density distribution of the inversion along with magnetic field streamlines are shown in Fig. 6.8 and Fig. 6.9. The density shows a structure with two more or less clear “branches”, which are the prominence feet, and that are connected at the apex. Notice that the density along the line of sight is confined in regions of similar size to the apparent size of the prominence feet in the plane of the sky. While this is a

FIGURE 6.9— Same as Fig. 6.8 but rotated 90° counterclockwise around the Y axis. The reference frame is indicated at the bottom left and the observer is along the positive Z axis.

reasonably to expect result, there is nothing in the code or in the setup that explicitly favors this result against others with more rarefied gas extended over more extensive regions along the LOS and resulting in similar optical thickness. Taking into account that the initial condition was an homogeneous distribution of the number density, this confinement along the line of sight must be due to the spatial coupling from potentially both the expansion in basis functions and the self-consistent RT in full 3D.

In Figs. 6.8-6.9 we also show the magnetic field lines in the inferred model. The magnetic field seems horizontal and almost parallel to the LOS in the regions of larger density, which are those contributing to the emergent Stokes profiles. We think that this result is not realistic. In the showcased inversion we are not enforcing the solenoidal condition of the magnetic field, so the magnetic field vector does not have any physical restriction besides fitting the polarization profiles. Because the critical Hanle field for the He I 10830 Å triplet is about 1 G, the triplet is in the saturation regime already at about 10 G. This introduces

a differential bias between the longitudinal and transversal component, as the former is mainly determined from the circular polarization via the Zeeman effect. The polarization spectrum is then only sensitive to the strength of the magnetic field along the LOS, as the Hanle effect is only sensitive to the direction of the magnetic field when in the saturation regime. In Fig. 6.10 we show a vector field for the transversal component of the magnetic field. We can see that this component is oriented in a direction closer to the vertical.

FIGURE 6.10— Density distribution as shown in Fig. 6.8 and vector field of the magnetic field component in the plane of the sky.

Finally, we get a velocity field with values between 2 and 6 km s⁻¹, which are rather small and mostly along the plane of the sky.

FIGURE 6.11— Density distribution as shown in Fig. 6.8 and field lines for the velocity vector.

6.5 Discussion

We have applied POLARIS to spectro-polarimetric data of a prominence. This data had been previously analyzed with the HaZeL code, applied pixel by pixel under the assumption of a constant property slab neglecting radiation transfer effects, finding a mostly vertical magnetic field forming a helical structure along the prominence feet. We have carried out the first ever 3D inversion taking into account self-consistent radiation transfer effects, accounting for atomic and scattering polarization, quantum interference, and the Zeeman and Hanle effects.

Due to time constraints, we have only been able to show the solution in a relatively smooth model with just 5^3 basis functions and without imposing the solenoidal condition of the magnetic field vector. However, we expect the inversion to improve even further when increasing the number of basis function and therefore the potential to reproduce features with smaller spatial resolution in the observation. Moreover, imposing the physical constraint of zero divergence

will likely help retrieving a more realistic spatial distribution of the magnetic field vector.

While computationally expensive, the application to real data of the POLARIS code demonstrate not only the capabilities of the meshfree technique to infer the plasma properties in a 3D volume, but the importance of taking into account the self-consistency radiation transfer, that spatially couples most regions in the prominences.

7

Conclusions

*To succeed, jump as quickly at opportunities
as you do at conclusions.*

Attributed to Benjamin Franklin (authorship not verified)

The magnetic field is central in many of the open problems in solar physics. Why is the temperature in the chromosphere and the corona larger than in the underlying photosphere? How is this temperature stratification maintained over the whole solar surface and over the whole solar cycle, almost independently of the degree of solar activity? If it is magnetic energy, how is this energy transported to the chromosphere and corona and how is it transformed into heat? How is the plasma in filaments and prominences supported against gravity for extended periods of time? How can they build up magnetic energy and eventually erupt as flares and coronal mass ejections? Why is there solar wind and how is it impacted by the magnetic field? Many of these open questions have important implications for the technological live on Earth, affected by the space weather, and its forecasting depends on our understanding of the magnetic field and our capability to infer it from observations.

The polarization of atomic and molecular lines in the solar spectrum encodes information about the magnetic field in their formation region in the solar atmosphere. Our most powerful tool to diagnose the magnetic field are inversion techniques, that is, algorithms capable of finding a model atmosphere such that, when solving the forward problem of the generation and transfer of polarized radiation under a set of assumptions, reproduce the observation. Of course, how good is the inference depends on the suitability of the assumptions.

However, solving the most general forward problem is prohibitively expensive from the computational point of view. For this reason inversion codes often need to compromise on the physics that are included, and strong approximations are sometimes considered. This is specially true when studying the upper photosphere, the chromosphere, or the corona, where radiation transfer effects can be critical. Due to this, and to the increasingly large volume of data on chromospheric lines that we expect from the current and future telescopes, there is a strong need to develop new techniques and tools that both accelerate existing inversion techniques and that allow for tackling the inference problem while accounting for critical physical ingredients that cannot be accounted for by the existing techniques.

After briefly introducing the theoretical background necessary for the thesis in chapter 2, we tackled the problem of accelerating the inversion of chromospheric lines in chapter 3. The bottleneck of NLTE inversions is the calculation of the gradient of the merit function, that entails solving the radiation transfer problem at every iteration of the inversion procedure, and for a number of models built by perturbing each of the free parameters of the inversion at least once (depending on the order of the finite differences).

Our acceleration strategy is based on skipping the calculation of the self-consistent solution in the forward problem. To this end we have devised an approach based on Graph Neural Networks to calculate departure coefficients from arbitrary stratifications of the atmospheric parameters. Calculating the solution of the radiative transfer equation once for a single direction (the line of sight) is really fast, and so are GNN in providing the output, potentially accelerating the inference by orders of magnitude. We have trained a GNN to solve the problem for the Ca II H, K, and infrared triplet levels. After demonstrating that the network is successful in providing the departure coefficients with enough accuracy, we applied an inversion code based on this GNN to real data on the Ca II line at 8542 Å. The comparison with the results of the STiC code, that actually solves the self-consistent problem, shows that the GNN code provides similar and robust results, but a factor of 10^3 faster.

While this technique cannot be straightforwardly applied to more complex lines (e.g., lines showing atomic polarization or partial frequency redistribution effects), it demonstrates the potential of machine learning techniques for the acceleration of the most computationally intensive parts of inversion techniques.

In chapter 4 we studied the impact of some of the most common approximations in the analysis of solar filaments. Most studies, which use observations in the He I triplet lines, are based on the constant property slab model under the assumption of negligible radiation transfer effects within the slab and,

therefore, of no differential illumination between the triplet components. We demonstrated that, for a constant property slab, radiation transfer and differential illumination effects in the He I 10830 Å triplet can have a significant impact on the emergent Stokes profiles, with potentially critical implications for the magnetic field diagnosis. This investigation further motivates the development of inference tools capable of accounting for radiation transfer effects in full 3D.

In chapter 5 we summarize the main aspects of our meshfree approach to the inversion problem, consisting in solving an unconstrained minimization problem in which the intermediate steps are not required to be NLTE consistent. This approach, which is the core of the POLARIS code, makes the inversion of spectropolarimetric data accounting for RT in 3D feasible. In order to improve our inference capabilities in filaments and prominences, we implemented the relevant equations in an atomic module for the POLARIS code for the He I 10830 Å triplet.

We have applied the POLARIS code to spectropolarimetric data of a solar prominence hosting a tornado in chapter 6. While time constraints have only allowed us to include an inversion with relatively low resolution (only 5^3 basis functions), the fit to the Stokes profiles is remarkable. Even though more iterations are needed to improve the self-consistency, and the model needs to be refined in terms of the number of basis functions, the density distribution of the inferred model is sound. Regarding the magnetic field, we have identified a potential bias on the longitudinal component that could be due to the formation of the line in the saturation regime. It is of great interest to check how the inferred magnetic field changes when forcing the solenoidal condition. We plan to continue improving the inversion of the prominence data by increasing the number of basis functions, and the result will be published in a scientific journal.

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